

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pilot Course on Entrepreneurship

Lecture Notes

D. Lupşa, A. Băicoianu, C. Mîzgaciu, M. Ivanovici, M. Voinea, D. Necşoi

Co-funded by
the European Union

The SEEN project received funding from the Erasmus+ programme under the grant agreement 2024-1-BG01-KA220-HED-000255491

Contents

1. Syllabus	iii
2. Authors' Biographies	iv
3. Dana Lupşa – <i>Entrepreneurship</i>	1
4. Alexandra Băicoianu, Camelia Mîzgaciu - <i>AI Tools for Entrepreneurs</i>	84
5. Mihai Ivanovici – <i>Research Project Management</i>	103
6. Mihaela Voinea - <i>Human Skills for Entrepreneurs</i>	143
7. Daniela Necşoi - <i>Team and Team Management</i>	157

Syllabus

D. Lupşa – *Entrepreneurship*

The module aims to impart knowledge and practical skills in the field of business, ranging from mindset and entrepreneurship way of thinking to complex business plans and testing business ideas. The participants will familiarize themselves with specific concepts in the economic field - for instance, SWOT analysis, business canvas, business plan template. The module is experiential and hands-on, with equal emphasis on how entrepreneurship will be taught and the students' experience, as well as on how the concepts can be applied in the current economic reality.

A. Băicoianu, C. Mîzgaciu – *AI Tools for Entrepreneurs*

The module introduces essential artificial intelligence (AI) concepts and provides hands-on experience with AI-driven tools to support entrepreneurial efforts. First, the module focuses on building a foundational understanding of AI, by combining theory with practical examples to highlight how AI is transforming industries. The second part focuses on applying AI in entrepreneurship, teaching participants to integrate AI into business planning, decision-making, and operations. The participant teams will create business plans using AI tools and present it during the "Delivering the pitches and feedback from the jury" session. They will pitch their ideas to knowledgeable reviewers, receiving feedback on technical implementation, business feasibility, customer impact, and ethical considerations.

M. Ivanovici – *Research Project Management. Theory and practical aspects*

Baby steps to addressing research project management, in terms of basic elements of a research project proposal. Practical aspects like the aim, objectives, project team and resources, GANTT chart, PERT, project budget, deliverables, as well as Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) identification and analysis and Intellectual Property protection.

M. Voinea – *Human skills for entrepreneurs*

The workshop will develop a deep and nuanced understanding of social competences in digitized world, in terms of competences, knowledge, skills (to analyse, to evaluate, to decide) and values (respect for difference, curiosity, social creativity, responsibility). It will help participants to understand the crucial importance of new social competences for a sustainable society. Debate: Why a new social ethic for 21st century? Participants will work in groups (4-6 persons) and will argue why is necessary a new social ethic, new competences as critical thinking, creativity, social responsibility.

D. Necşoi – *Team and team management*

Foundations of team and teamwork: what are teams and why (and when) are they important? How to build a team. The developmental stages of a team. Team effectiveness (principles for building an effective team/ team processes and dynamics/ team working skills and attributes in order to be effective as a team and as a team member: sharing ideas, assertiveness, leadership, cooperation, solving conflicts, etc.

Authors' biographies

Dana Adriana Lupșa-Tătaru is an associate professor with a PhD in management at the Faculty of Economic Sciences and Business Administration at Transilvania University of Brașov. She teaches courses on Entrepreneurship, Organizational Communication and Management. She coordinates the Bachelor's degree program in Business Administration and the postgraduate program Up to Start - Entrepreneurial Competencies. She collaborates with the Brașov Chamber of Commerce and Industry with schools and public institutions in Brașov, Romania.

Alexandra Băicoianu holds a PhD in Computer Science from Babeș-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca. She is currently an Associate Professor in the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science at Transilvania University of Brașov. Her research interest and expertise are in the field of machine learning, formal languages and compilers, algorithms, remote sensing and Earth Observation data, autonomous driving, electric and hybrid vehicles. She is particularly focused on the practical applications and implementation of these topics, bridging theoretical research with real-world practice.

Camelia Mîzgaciu is a lecturer at the Department of Management and Economic Informatics at Transilvania University of Brașov and holds a PhD in Computer Science from the same university. She has contributed to nine national projects, acting as a researcher or IT specialist. Her research interests include graph theory, operational research, network optimization and decision modeling. She has authored and co-authored over 24 scientific articles published in peer-reviewed journals and proceedings of national and international conferences.

Mihaela Voinea holds a PhD in Education Sciences from the University of Bucharest, Romania. She is an assistant professor at Transilvania University of Brașov, in the Psychology, Education and Teacher Training Department and has more than 15 years of experience in the educational field. Her research interests focus on the field of teacher education, intercultural education and critical thinking. She was involved in various educational projects, funded by the Ministry of Education and Research as a researcher or a trainer. She is involved as an educational specialist in the development of the new curricula for social education for second level and supervises methodical-scientific thesis for obtaining the first teaching degree.

Daniela Necșoi is assistant professor at Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences at Transilvania University of Brașov. She holds a PhD in educational sciences from University of Bucharest, Romania. She develops educational activities for in-service and prospective teachers from early and primary school, middle, and secondary school. She cooperates with the Teaching-Staff Resource Centre of Brașov in creating and delivering professional continuous training programs for teachers. Her research interests include educational management and methodology of teaching. She is the author and coauthor of 6 books and book chapters, over 25 articles published in scientific journals or international conferences.

Mihai Ivanovici holds a PhD in electronics from Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania. He is a full professor within the Department of Electronics and Computers, Transilvania University of Brașov, România. He has 20 years of experience in managing research projects. He is head of ISOP research laboratory, and member of the IEEE Signal Processing and IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing societies. His research interest and expertise are in the field of image processing and analysis. He is supervising PhD in the field of electronics, telecommunications and information technologies.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universitatea
Transilvania
din Braşov

Entrepreneurship

Dana LUPŞA

7-8 April 2025

Entrepreneurship
Braşov
7-8 April 2025

Dana Lupşa

Day 1, 7th of April 2025	Day 2, 8th of April 2025
09.00 - 10.30 1.1. Mindset, thinking and action	09.00 - 10.30 2.1. The art of pitching
10.30 - 11.00 Coffee break	10.30 - 11.00 Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30 1.2. Opportunity evaluation	11.00 - 12.30 2.2. Business plan (1)
12.30 - 13.30 Lunch break	12.30 - 13.30 Lunch break
13.30 - 15.00 1.3. Business models	13.30 - 15.00 2.3. Business plan (2)
15.00 - 15.30 Coffee break	15.00 - 15.30 Coffee break
15.30 - 17.00 1.4. Market tests	15.30 - 17.00 2.4. Business plan (3)

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.1. Entrepreneurial mindset, thinking and action

Co-funded by
the European Union

For students:

How might we use an entrepreneurial mindset to develop a business?

Co-funded by
the European Union

“We are all entrepreneurs but too few people get to practice it.”
Muhammad Yunus

Are you ready to get started?

Co-funded by
the European Union

RULES OF THE ROAD

- Our roles as **facilitators**
 - Learn and flourish
- Your roles as a **participant**
 - No **bystanders** - everyone has a role to play!
 - **Stretch** yourself
 - Let's get **uncomfortable!**

Co-funded by
the European Union

How entrepreneurial are you?

Co-funded by the European Union

The boat exercise

Co-funded by the European Union

AS EDUCATORS, WE HAVE TO HAVE ENTREPRENEURIAL MINDSET,
TO THINK AND ACT LIKE AN ENTREPRENEUR
TO DEVELOP THE ENTREPRENEURIAL SPIRIT OF OUR STUDENTS!

Co-funded by
the European Union

HOW one
teaches is just
as important as
WHAT one
teaches

Co-funded by
the European Union

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

Co-funded by the European Union

THE JOURNEY

Co-funded by the European Union

Start with what you have

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Be the only

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Start with what you have
Create the future
Be the only
Action trumps everything

Co-funded by the European Union

Experiencing entrepreneurial mindset

Part 1: Complete a jigsaw puzzle as quickly as you can.

Part 2: Draw a story to represent your table group

Co-funded by the European Union

What did you prefer working on?

Putting together
a jigsaw puzzle

Drawing a story

Co-funded by
the European Union

Two ways of thinking

Puzzle

MANAGERIAL
(prediction)

Stories

ENTREPRENEURIAL
(creation)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Prof. Phil Kim, Symposium for entrepreneurship educators, Babson College, 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

Both ways of thinking are necessary and important

Puzzle

(prediction)

Stories

(creation)

Co-funded by the European Union

Entrepreneurship is a way of thinking, acting and being that combines the ability to find or create new opportunities with the **courage** to act on them.

Neck, Neck, & Murray (2021) Entrepreneurship: The Practice & Mindset (2nd ed). Sage Publishing

Co-funded by
the European Union

What skills should the *student of the future* develop and master in order to succeed after graduation?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Businesses' top 10 skill priorities for 2027

1. Curiosity and lifelong learning	
2. Technological literacy	
3. Design and user experience	
4. Motivation and self-awareness	
5. Empathy and active listening	

Type of skill

■ Cognitive skills
 ■ Self-efficacy
 ■ Technology skills
 ■ Working with others

Source
World Economic Forum, Future of Jobs Report 2023.

Note
The skills which organizations will prioritize in workforce development initiatives from 2023 to 2027

Co-funded by
the European Union

Businesses' top 10 skill priorities for 2027

1. Curiosity and lifelong learning	
2. Technological literacy	
3. Design and user experience	
4. Motivation and self-awareness	
5. Empathy and active listening	

Type of skill

■ Cognitive skills
 ■ Self-efficacy
 ■ Technology skills
 ■ Working with others

Source
World Economic Forum, Future of Jobs Report 2023.

Note
The skills which organizations will prioritize in workforce development initiatives from 2023 to 2027

Which skills can be thought from your course now?

All skills involve entrepreneurial mindset.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Now more than ever, the world needs
entrepreneurs of all kinds
who think and act entrepreneurially—
who can transform opportunity into reality, and
create social and economic value
for themselves and for others.

Prof. Phil Kim, Symposium for entrepreneurship educators, Babson College, 2024

Co-funded by
the European Union

Which part of
this definition
resonates
with you?

Co-funded by
the European Union

What's my why? My desired impact? North star? I want to...How might I... I have a desire to... (Important: This is not an idea.)

What do I have today that can support my why? Who am I? What do I know? Whom do I know?

Description of the idea today. (The idea will change or shape with action so don't get stuck here.)

BABSON COLLEGE

Entrepreneurial Thought & Action

WORKSHEET

What did I learn from my actions and how does this shape my idea? What am I going to do next?

Do not write in this space until actions have been taken.

HAPPY METER

1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10

circle number only after completing worksheet

© Heidi M. Neck, Babson College [5.22]

ACT, LEARN, BUILD / PIVOT, REPEAT

These are my first (or next) 3 actions to learn about and shape my idea. What are my asks? (Think about 3 questions and what actions you will take to get answers?)

(1) _____

(2) _____

(3) _____

Who can I enroll? Who do I need that is not in my current network? Where can I get buy-in?

What can I afford to lose to take the above actions? What am I willing to invest in order to learn?

Time (how much?)

Money (how much?)

Social capital (how much?)

Entrep.
thought

Entrep.
action

Entrepreneurship is about practicing *creating, finding and exploiting opportunities.*

Entrepreneurs *act*, entrepreneurs *learn*, entrepreneurs *build*(in this order)."

Recap

- 4 principles
- Entrepreneurship
- ETA

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.2. Opportunity evaluation

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- You have to decide upon a team leader.
- The team leader thinks of a food business.
- Every team member has 5 questions to ask, the team leader may only use YES or NO to answer.
- Guess the dish!

Co-funded by the European Union

? What's my why? My desired impact? North star? I want to... How might I... I have a desire to... (Important: This is not an idea.)

🔍 What do I have today that can support my why? Who am I? What do I know? Whom do I know?

💡 Description of the idea today. (The idea will change or shape with action so don't get stuck here.)

BABSON COLLEGE
Entrepreneurial Thought & Action
WORKSHEET

🔄 What did I learn from my actions and how does this shape my idea? What am I going to do next?
Do not write in this space until actions have been taken.

HAPPY METER
☹️ 1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10 ☺️
circle number only after completing worksheet

🎬 These are my first (or next) 3 actions to learn about and shape my idea. What are my asks? (Think about 3 questions and what actions you will take to get answers?)

[1]

[2]

[3]

🌐 Who can I enroll? Who do I need that is not in my current network? Where can I get buy-in?

⬇️ What can I afford to lose to take the above actions? What am I willing to invest in order to learn?

Time (how much?)

Money (how much?)

Social capital (how much?)

Co-funded by the European Union

© Hadi M. Neki, Babson College (v5.22)
ACT
LEARN
BUILD / PIVOT
REPEAT

How can you evaluate if an idea is an actual business opportunity?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Big failures

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5lutHF5HhVA>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Big failures

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TkhWonFm-Lw&t=33s>

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Prof. Phil Kim, Symposium for entrepreneurship educators, Babson College, 2024

<p>Understanding the problem and customer: What is the core problem or pain point your idea addresses? Who experiences this problem most acutely? (Demographics, behavior, needs) How does the customer describe this problem in their own words? What are the causes of this problem?</p>	<p>Assessing customer motivation: What frustrates your customer most about their current solution (or lack of one)? What emotional or practical outcomes does your customer desire? What objections might they have about trying your solution?</p>	<p>Evaluating your solution: What is your unique competitive advantage in solving this problem? How does your solution improve on what exists? What specific benefits does your solution provide to your customer? What is the learning curve for using your solution?</p>
<p>Market validation: How many people or businesses share this problem? Is the problem frequent enough to warrant a solution? Is the problem growing, shrinking, or shifting?</p>	<p>Feasibility and execution: What resources do you need to build and scale this solution? What partnerships or expertise are essential for success? What could go wrong in execution, and how will you address it?</p>	<p>Financial viability: What is the customer willing to pay for this solution? What is the cost of acquiring customers? What is your profit margin, and how sustainable is it?</p>
<p>Testing assumptions: What key assumptions are you making about the customer or market? How can you test these assumptions quickly and cheaply? What data or feedback will validate your idea as an opportunity?</p>		

Co-funded by the European Union

Business idea

- Think of a business idea.
- Answer the previous questions.
- Decide either it is an opportunity to develop for the next 2 days

Co-funded by the European Union

Is feed resource recovery a business opportunity?

Co-funded by the European Union

Source: IDEO Human Centered Design Toolkit

Co-funded by the European Union

Feed resource recovery - 1

1. Who is the customer?
2. How will they use this concept?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Feed resource recovery - 2

1. What's the problem?
2. What's anaerobic digestion?
3. Is this an opportunity?
4. On which three criteria is it weakest?
5. On which three criteria is it strongest?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Opportunity checklist

- Understand the dimensions of an opportunity
- Develop awareness of better vs weaker opportunities
- Determine their “affordable loss”

Opportunity checklist

Customer	Better opportunity	Weaker opportunity
Identifiable	Defined core customer	Undefined core customer
Demographics	Clearly defined and focused	Fuzzy definition and unfocused
Psychographics	Clearly defined and focused	Fuzzy definition and unfocused
Trends		
Macro trends	Multiple and converging	Few and disparate
Target market	Multiple and converging	Few and disparate
Window of opportunity	Opening	Closing
Market structure	Emerging	Mature/decline
Market growth		
Rate	20% or greater	Less than 20%
Price/value		
Value	Fully reflected in price	Penetration pricing
Volume	Very high	Moderate
Competition		
Market structure	Emerging	Mature
Number of direct competitors	Few	Many
Number of substitutes products/services	Few	Many
Strength of competitors	Weak	Strong
Vendors		
Relative power	Weak	Strong
Government		
Regulations	Low	High
Taxes	Low	High
Global environment		
Customers	Interested and accessible	Not interested and accessible
Competition	Nonexistent or weak	Existing and strong
Vendors	Eager	Unavailable

Prof. Phil Kim, Symposium for entrepreneurship educators, Babson College, 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

Feed resource recovery - 2

- **Read:** mini-case
- **Complete** the checklist on your own
- **Discuss** with 2-3 other colleagues about your selections
- **Decide** on your overall assessment

- Investor
- Customer
- Supplier
- Other perspective

Co-funded by the European Union

Shane's opportunity tests back then

- Business Plan contests
- 1st at Rice, 2nd at Babson, Colorado and Berkeley
- Secured Massachusetts Technology Collaborative Grant to test feasibility (\$20k)
- Seeks \$250k to build fully functional prototype

Co-funded by
the European Union

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CE_qcJGVW3E

Co-funded by
the European Union

The opportunity - today

- <http://www.divertinc.com/>
- Divert has raised a total funding of \$1B over 2 rounds.
- Its first funding round was on Jul 24, 2018.
- The core customer are grocery stores
- The decentralized systems weren't efficient (each store doesn't produce enough waste)
- Operates as hub-spoke at central distribution centers
- Trucks take food and product to store, return with waste

Co-funded by
the European Union

Opportunity checklist

- Use opportunity checklist for your own business idea.
- Decide on the overall assessment.

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.3. Business models

Co-funded by the European Union

- 1. 🍔 👑
- 2. 💉 👄
- 3. 🟠 🐮
- 4. 🎲 🎲 🍕
- 5. ⭐ 💰
- 6. 👁️ 🐝 ♍️
- 7. ✖️ 📦
- 8. 🟩 🍓
- 9. 👁️ 🔑 🅐
- 10. ⬇️ 🏠

Co-funded by the European Union

1. 🍔 👑
2. 💉 👄
3. 🟠 🐂
4. 🎲 🎲 🍕
5. ⭐ 📄
6. 👁️ 🐝 ♍️
7. ✖️ 📦
8. 🖥️ 🍓
9. 👁️ 🔑 📌
10. ⬇️ 🖨️

1. Burger King
2. Phillips
3. Redbull
4. Domino's Pizza
5. Starbucks
6. IBM
7. X-Box
8. Blackberry
9. IKEA
10. Subway

Co-funded by
the European Union

Source – IDEO Human centered design toolkit

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a business model

Value Proposition

A business model describes the rationale of how an organization **creates, delivers, and captures** value.

Revenue Model

<http://www.businessmodelgeneration.com/book>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Value proposition

“Creating value for others” =
Meet needs, solve problems,
and alleviate pain points

BABSON COLLEGE
© Philip H. Kahn

Co-funded by
the European Union

How do we determine what is valued?

Customers and users hire a product/service
for a “job to be done”

- Understand the **why** behind the **hire**

BABSON COLLEGE
© Phillip H. Kim

Co-funded by
the European Union

Value proposition

The reasons why customers buy or use
your product/service

Co-funded by
the European Union

FUNCTIONALITY

Features you want or need
to get the “job done”

Co-funded by
the European Union

EXPERIENCE

Memorable event, process, or encounter that
provides positive emotions

Co-funded by
the European Union

DESIGN

Attractive aesthetic features and qualities

Co-funded by
the European Union

RELIABILITY

Features work correctly & effectively, when
you need it the most to get the job done

Co-funded by
the European Union

CONVENIENCE

Easy, accessible to use to get the job done

Co-funded by
the European Union

COST REDUCTION

Saves you money

Co-funded by
the European Union

PRICE

It's the right (lowest) price for what you need to get the job done

Co-funded by
the European Union

Value proposition

Functionality
Experience
Design
Reliability
Convenience
Cost Reduction
Price

BARSON COLLEGE
© PHILIP H. KIM

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

- Decide what is the value proposition for each of the following products/services.
- If there are more than 1, choose the most important one.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

HYPE

**Joining a trend, conferring status, or avoiding
the fear of missing out (FOMO)**

Co-funded by
the European Union

Value proposition

A value proposition is a statement or short paragraph that:

- Clearly describes what a service, business or organization offers.
- Who benefits from it.
- Why it is beneficial to those people.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Value proposition

Value propositions typically follow this format:

Our “product/service” help(s) “customer segment” who want to “customer’s jobs to do/problems to solve” by “your verb” and “your verb, “unlike “competing value proposition.”

For example, Amazon’s value proposition for customers might be:

- Our **online marketplace** helps **shoppers** who want to **purchase goods online** by **offering a vast selection of products and a convenient shopping experience**, unlike **traditional retail experiences or smaller online platforms**.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

What is the value proposition for your business opportunity?

Remember the basic categories:

- Functionality
- Experience
- Design
- Reliability
- Convenience
- Cost Reduction
- Price
- Hype
- Sustainability/social impact

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a business model?

Value Proposition

*A business model describes the rationale of how an organization **creates, delivers, and captures** value.*

Revenue Model

Source: Osterwalder & Pigneur, Business Model Generation

<http://www.businessmodelgeneration.com/book>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Revenue model

The framework used to charge customers for the *value* you create for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Unit/hourly

Charge based on quantity (units or hourly).

Co-funded by
the European Union

Advertising

Charge third-party for access to promote their product/service.

Co-funded by the European Union

Franchise/licensing

Charge for the right to use a product/service, concept, content or technology

Co-funded by the European Union

Subscription

Charge a set fee on a regular schedule and (typically) in advance of when the product/service is used

Co-funded by the European Union

Transaction fee

Charge for bringing together two or more parties in a transaction

Co-funded by the European Union

Professional fee

Deloitte.

Charge by a service, job or project

Co-funded by
the European Union

Revenue models

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

- Imagine starting a street food business – pick your favorite one!
- Describe how to use each revenue model

Unit/hourly
Advertising
Franchising/Licensing
Subscription
Transaction Fee
Professional Fee

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

What is the revenue model for your business opportunity?

Remember the basic categories:

- Unit/hourly
- Advertising
- Franchising/Licensing
- Subscription
- Transaction Fee
- Professional Fee

Co-funded by
the European Union

Recap

- Value proposition

- Functionality
- Experience
- Design
- Reliability
- Convenience
- Cost Reduction
- Price
- Hype
- Sustainability/social impact

- Revenue models

- Unit/hourly
- Advertising
- Franchising/Licensing
- Subscription
- Transaction Fee
- Professional Fee

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.4. Market tests

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

Think of **famous business** that you know information about.

The first player's sentence of the scene begins with an "A", the second with a "B", and so on through the alphabet. The final sentence/speech of the scene must begin with a "Z".

For instance

- A fun challenge. **Boy**, this fun game challenges the players to create dialogue that follows the sequence of the alphabet. **Can** you do it? **Do** try it. **Enjoy**. For a few variations, look below. **Go** ahead and create your own. **Have** a blast.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Source – IDEO Human centered design toolkit

Co-funded by
the European Union

Rapid prototyping

1. Find the quickest path to experience
2. Doing is the best kind of thinking.

“Maximize the rate of learning by minimizing the time to try ideas”
(Tom Chi, Google)

Co-funded by
the European Union

amazonPrime

When Amazon considered launching Amazon Prime, it was a **one-way door decision**—a major, irreversible choice that would fundamentally change its business model.

Once introduced, offering **unlimited fast shipping for a fixed price** would permanently impact customer expectations and logistics costs. If it failed, reversing the program would damage customer trust.

Co-funded by
the European Union

On the other hand, smaller features within Prime, like **Prime Video** or **Prime Day**, were **two-way door decisions**—easier to test and adjust.

If Prime Video didn't gain traction, Amazon could tweak its content strategy or pricing. If Prime Day wasn't profitable, they could scale it differently or discontinue it.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Principles

“Perfect is the enemy of the good”

Red-Green Cycle Development

Red: Design the minimum

Green: Test to make it work

Cycle: Optimize once it works

Co-funded by
the European Union

Storyboards

Co-funded by
the European Union

Paper/crafts

Co-funded by
the European Union

Wireframes

Co-funded by
the European Union

Videos

How to create prototype for business

Vizionează >

Co-funded by
the European Union

Solar trash compactor

- Read the *Solar powered trash can* handout
- Discuss two ways to prototype this concept Quickly
- Cheaply
- Develop a plan to share this prototype with users.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Concept experiments

<http://thecityofseligman.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Document.jpg>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Smoke testing

<https://flaglerlive.com/wp-content/uploads/smoke-testing-palm-coast.jpg>

Co-funded by
the European Union

One very important question

- Will they buy and use your solution?

instead of

- Do you think they will buy and use your solution?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Smoke testing

Co-funded by
the European Union

EXPERIMENT CANVAS		DESIGN A BETTER BUSINESS
<p>RISKIEST ASSUMPTION What is the riskiest assumption you want to test?</p>	<p>RESULTS Record the qualitative or quantitative results of the experiment</p>	<p>CONCLUSION Did your results match your hypothesis? Or did they contradict your hypothesis? And was your result clear enough?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> VALIDATED</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> INVALIDATED</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> INCONCLUSIVE</p>
<p>FALSIFIABLE HYPOTHESIS Construct your hypothesis</p> <p>We believe that < specific, testable action ></p> <p>Will drive < specific, measurable outcome ></p> <p>Within < timeframe ></p>	<p>EXPERIMENT SETUP What kind of experiment will you use? What are you measuring? How many times?</p>	
<p>NEXT STEPS What is your next move?</p>		

© BY DESIGNABETTERBUSINESS.COM

The world is a network and it is a network. Copyright Attribution: Stanford University, 2010. Stanford University is a registered trademark of Stanford University. 171 Second Street, Suite 300, San Francisco, California, 94105, USA.

The Experiment Canvas was created by Neil Young.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

- For your business opportunity, fill in the experiment canvas.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

YODA - collect Your Own Data

Co-funded by
the European Union

Smoke test techniques to collect YODA

- Pinocchio
- Mechanical Turk
- Fake Door

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pinocchio

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pinocchio

Create a **non-functional prototype** to test user interest or gather feedback on the concept.

Example: testing a new smart fitness wearable.

- Develop a physical mock-up (replica) of the wearable device that looks and feels like the real product but lacks any internal functionality.
- Present the mock-up to potential customers in a gym or at an expo, asking for feedback on its design, size, and potential features, *to gauge interest and identify design improvements* before investing in full product development.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Mechanical Turk

Co-funded by
the European Union

Mechanical Turk

Simulate an automated process with human intervention to understand customer behavior or validate workflows.

Example: testing an AI-powered resume review service.

- Create a landing page for the service and invite users to upload their resumes for analysis. Instead of using AI, a human expert reviews the resumes behind the scenes and provides feedback to users.

Monitor user engagement, track sign-ups, and collect feedback on the service experience, *to validate demand for the service and identify key features* that users expect from the AI tool before building the technology.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Fake door

Co-funded by
the European Union

Fake door

Offer a service or product that doesn't yet exist to test demand.

Example: launching an online course on data analytics.

- Add a course titled "Mastering Data Analytics" to your website with a "**Register Now**" button. Once users click, display a message: "We're finalizing the course. Sign up to be notified when it's live!"
- Measure the number of clicks and email sign-ups to assess interest in the course, *to determine if there's sufficient demand* to justify creating the course.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Create your own 30 in 30 smoke tests

Smoke test your business opportunity

- (a) Prepare at least one hypothesis
- (b) Design a test to collect YODA
- (c) Repeat (a) and (b) until you get enough data to make a decision.

Co-funded by
the European Union

SOLAR TRASH COMPACTOR - SMOKE TEST

- How would you smoke test this concept?
 - Quickly
 - Cheaply
 - “30 in 30 Test”
- What information do you need to test?
- How will you collect this information?
- What will you do?

Co-funded by
the European Union

SOLAR TRASH COMPACTOR – EARLY TESTS

- Validate idea with summer intern – Spire Solar
- Talk with professors
- Sell co-founder
- Get two Olin engineering students to help build proof-of-concept
 - Build proof of concept using kitchen trash compactors
- Business plan competition
- Sell first customer (Vail Ski Resort)
- Cad drawings
- Find design/manufacturer partner
- Deliver product and redesign
- Raise seed capital to build first 100 units
- Sell units

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Recap

- Rapid prototyping, storyboards, paper craft, wireframes, videos
- Smoke testing
- YODA

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.5. The art of pitching

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- Think of your own professional path and decide upon two facts and one fiction.
- Take a turn and share them with the group.
- Other players must decide which statements are real, and which are inventions.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The art of pitching

WHEN AND HOW DO YOU SPEAK IN YOUR CLASSES?

- Do they ask questions when you lecture?
- Do you ask them questions throughout your lectures?
- Do you require them to make presentations? If so, what kind?
- In what other ways do they speak during your classes?

The Art of the Pitch presentation was created by Heidi Neck, Ph.D., the Jeffrey A. Timmons Professor of Entrepreneurial Studies at Babson College. It has been modified by Professor Mark Rice for the Romanian SEE Program and by Assoc.prof. Dana Lupşa.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The art of pitching

GROUP EXERCISE #1

#1: In what ways do you struggle when they make presentations?

#2: What can you do to become better speakers?

AFTER THE DISCUSSION, EACH GROUP WILL PRESENT ONE CHALLENGE THEY HAVE WHEN MAKING PRESENTATIONS AND A POSSIBLE APPROACH YOU MIGHT IMPLEMENT TO OVERCOME IT.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The art of pitching

PROFESSOR RICE'S EXPERIENCE: STUDENT SPEAKING CHALLENGES

- Poor Structure
- Too much content.
- Lack of attention to making three key points. (What will the audience remember a week, month or year later?)
- Lack of a compelling ending. (Call for action or compelling summary.)
- Poorly prepared slides and other supporting materials.
- Failure to engage the audience.
- Facing the screen and reading the text on the slides.
- Failure to anticipate questions and to prepare / practice responses.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The art of pitching

SOME POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

- Provide knowledge about effective presentations.
- Emphasize the importance of practicing before presenting.
- Give them multiple opportunities to present.
- Provide positive and constructive feedback after each presentation – from the professor, peers, and potentially from outside guest experts.
- Give them the opportunity to present again after responding to feedback.
- Send them to your Speech Center for help – if your university has one.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The art of pitching

gettyimages

Entrepreneurs must be able to articulate their ideas in a “pitch” to all kinds of “catchers”.

The pitch is used to obtain all kinds of important start-up resources:

- Investors and start-up \$\$
- Co-founders and key employees in the early stages of the venture
- Advisers
- First customers
- Key suppliers

Co-funded by
the European Union

Enrolling the appropriate and necessary stakeholders

3 Important Skills to Learn

- Develop the pitch so that it aligns with the needs of the target audience.
- Prepare and practice the pitch to ensure that it is compelling.
- First impressions matter.

Co-funded by
the European Union

A Quiz on FIRST Impressions

- 10** How many seconds does it take to create first impression?
- 93** What % of first impressions are based on non-verbal communication (how you sit/stand, your body posture, eye contact, or handshake)?
- 55** What % of first impressions has to do with physical aspects (clothing, dress)?
- 36** What % increase in positive first impressions occurs by using someone's name
- 38** What % increase in positive first impressions occurs by using an "appealing" tone of voice (relaxed, friendly, enthusiastic)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let's practice

Create the elevator pitch for AirBnB

Elevator Pitch sentence structure:
FOR (target customer), WHO HAS (customer need), (product name) IS A (market category) THAT (one key benefit).
UNLIKE (competition), THE PRODUCT (unique differentiator).

Co-funded by the European Union

Who wants to volunteer to read the Elevator Pitch sentence they created for this exercise?

For the adventure traveler who wants to stay in local accommodations, Airbnb is a lodging rental platform that connects renters to travelers that do not want to stay in traditional hotels.

(Professor Heidi Neck)

Elevator Pitch sentence structure:
FOR (target customer), WHO HAS (customer need), (product name) IS A (market category) THAT (one key benefit).
UNLIKE (competition), THE PRODUCT (unique differentiator).

Co-funded by the European Union

Types of Pitches

- There are different types of pitches
 - 1 minute elevator pitch
 - 3 minute rocket pitch
 - Initial investor pitch (30-45 mins) including discussion. (The pitch will be much shorter perhaps 10-15 minutes.)

Co-funded by
the European Union

An effective pitch includes the following six components:

1. The market opportunity (the customer "point of pain")
2. Value proposition and customer target (product-market fit)
3. Market size
4. Revenue model
5. Founder/Team Background
6. Call to action

Co-funded by
the European Union

Depending on the audience, not all six components may be required – and perhaps others should be added.

Designing the Pitch should start with understanding the needs and expectations of the audience. (You are the seller and the audience is the buyer.)

You also need to decide what are the most important messages you need to convey.

Co-funded by
the European Union

EXERCISE #3: Rocket Pitch Preparation and practice

Each group should assume that you have been hired by UNITBV to help with marketing SEEN Project globally – in recognition of your outstanding performance in the Romania.

Several faculty colleagues at another university ask you the following question. "Can you give us an example of a learning experience in in this project that you found compelling and that you think is representative of the overall value of the project?"

Prepare a 3-minute rocket pitch addressing only #1, #2, #5 and #6 below. Decide who in your Group will make the pitch, if I call on you.

1. The market opportunity (the customer "point of pain", i.e. how might faculty feel dissatisfied that would cause them to seek out development opportunities like this program?
2. Value proposition and customer target (product-market fit). For this element of your rocket pitch, use the format of the Elevator Pitch sentence.
3. Market size
4. Revenue model →
5. Founder/Team Background.
(You can assume the team is Dana and Mihai.)
6. Call to action

Elevator Pitch sentence structure:

FOR (target customer), WHO HAS (customer need), (product name) IS A (market category) THAT (one key benefit).
UNLIKE (competition), THE PRODUCT (unique differentiator).

Co-funded by
the European Union

What do investors look for in a pitch?

*Rank the order of importance
(1=most important, 10=least important) of these 10 qualities:*

RANK	QUALITY
	Entrepreneur is passionate
	Company has good revenue potential
	Entrepreneur is coachable
	Company has good business model
	Company has reasonable barriers to entry
	Entrepreneur is trustworthy
	Entrepreneur is enthusiastic
	Company has reasonable exit plan
	Entrepreneur is experienced
	Company has large growth potential

Co-funded by
the European Union

133

What do investors look for in a pitch?

*Rank the order of importance
(1=most important, 10=least important) of these 10 qualities:*

RANK	QUALITY
9	Entrepreneur is passionate
2	Company has good revenue potential
4	Entrepreneur is coachable
1	Company has good business model
7	Company has reasonable barriers to entry
3	Entrepreneur is trustworthy
8	Entrepreneur is enthusiastic
5	Company has reasonable exit plan
10	Entrepreneur is experienced
6	Company has large growth potential

Co-funded by
the European Union

The Story

- ➔ • The story is what gets peoples interest.
- ➔ • It is like a novel, not a documentary.

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of The Story

- **The Product**
 - Not the technology. (An invention does not make a company. Without money, there is no company.)
 - Not your idea.
- **But**
 - What are you going to put into a box at the end of the day that UPS is going to pick-up and deliver to your customer?
 - What problem are you solving for your customer?
 - Why is the customer going to buy it?

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of The Story

- **The Market**

- Not that there are 400 billion potential customers.
- Not that you have no competition.

- **But**

- What does your customer look like?
- Who are the first 5 people you are going to call on?
- What are the market dynamics?
- What is the competition going to do?
- Not that you are the lowest selling price.

How might an entrepreneur identify the first five potential customers to call on?

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of The Story

- **The Team**

- Not that you are smarter than everyone else.
- Not your life history.

- **But**

- What is the teams' relevant experience?
- Who is going to be the queen or the king?
- What draft picks do you need?

Why do investors want to know who is going to be the queen (or the king)?

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of The Story

- **The Financials**
 - Not that you are going to be a \$2 billion company in 5 years.
 - Not that you have better gross margins than everyone else.
 - Not that your SG&A costs are lowest in the industry.
- **But**
 - How fast can you really grow?
 - What are your real COGS?
 - Make it believable!

How will a venture capitalist respond if you state:

"I will grow this business to \$5 million in annual revenues by the end of my tenth year in business. And I only need \$10M of investment from you?"

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of The Story

- Product or service – Makes the sale
- Market opportunity – Closes the deal
- Entrepreneurial team – Defines the terms
- Financials – Maintains your credibility

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

REMEMBER

When you are raising capital, your company is the “product” you are selling. The investor is your customer.

© Bela Musits 2009

Co-funded by
the European Union

Coachability and Trustworthiness

For investors, evaluating a pitch is just as much about evaluating the person as well as evaluating the business opportunity!

Co-funded by
the European Union

Recap

- Pitches – types and components

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.6. Business plans (1)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- A player state a business goal they want to achieve a year from now.
- The next player says, “Unfortunately...” and improvises an obstacle that might get in the way of achieving that goal.
- The first player then responds by saying “Yes and...” and improvising a way they overcame that obstacle.
- Continue around the circle so that the player can refute and overcome all possible obstacles that would come between them and their goal, however wild or difficult.

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a Business?

*Imagine you need to make money tomorrow without a job
– how would you do it?*

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a Business?

“Creating value for others” =
Meet needs, solve problems,
and alleviate pain points

BABSON COLLEGE
© Philip H. Kim

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gi7Vy_2B_D8

Lean canvas

The **Lean Canvas** is designed specifically for **startups** and **early-stage businesses**.

It focuses on identifying key risks and testing assumptions quickly. Created by **Ash Maurya**, the Lean Canvas replaces some sections of the Business Model Canvas to be **more problem-solution focused**.

Lean canvas

https://www.dochub.com/fillable-form/80342-lean-canvas-template?msclkid=ae9f9af20f411aa22c05fd1f02b99f7d&utm_source=bing&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=DocHub%20Forms%20-%20Dynamic&utm_term=dochub.com%2Ffillable-form%2F&utm_content=DocHub%20Forms%20-%20Dynamic

Let's practice

Fill in the Lean canvas form for your business opportunity.

Co-funded by
the European Union

1.7. Business plans (2)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- The first person starts by saying "remember the time..." and introducing a shared (fictional) memory the group has of something they did together (e.g. "Remember the time we went to that street fair, and it was a really hot day?").
- That person calls someone else's name, and the next person adds details.
- In this way, each person says 1-3 sentences, building out the story.

Co-funded by the European Union

Lean canvas vs. Business canvas

Lean Canvas	Business Model Canvas
Startup-focused	Established businesses
Problem-oriented	Value-oriented
Adds Key Metrics & Unfair Advantage	Focuses on Partnerships & Resources
Rapid testing & iteration	Structured, long-term planning

Co-funded by the European Union

1.8. Business plans (3)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Business plan template

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- Choose something from your desk.
- You get 30 seconds to prepare a pitch to sell the object to your teammates.
- Then have another 60 seconds to persuade your teammates to buy that item.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pitching

Co-funded by
the European Union

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gXwewPgLmkE>

Pitching

Your slides and presentation should address the following:

- Clear articulation of the **idea**
- What **problem** does it solve?
- How does it **work**?
- What **resources** are needed to implement?
- How will you **acquire** the resources?
- What **value** does it bring to entrepreneurship education?
- What's your **first actionable step**?

Other notes

- Team pitches
- 3 minute presentation with 5 minutes of Q&A

Co-funded by
the European Union

Preparing for Rocket Pitch

- Team pitches
- Your business idea
- 3 minutes
- Your rocket pitch will be a "gift".

Co-funded by
the European Union

A gift must be packaged!

- Clear articulation of the idea
- What need is being met and for whom?
- What is the value proposition?
- What resources are needed to implement?
- How will you acquire the resources?
- What value does it bring to entrepreneurship education?
- What's your first actionable step?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Apply Five Tips to Make Your Presentation Great

Co-funded by
the European Union

Rocket Pitch Work

- Each team will present a pitch for the business opportunity.
- Your pitch can last no longer than 5 minutes, so practice it to make sure you can do it in 5 minutes or less.
- During this session, I will circulate among the teams – asking questions and providing guidance.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Tools for entrepreneurs

Alexandra Băicoianu
Camelia Mîzgăciu

9 April 2025

1

WHAT IS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE?

Artificial Intelligence (AI), a term coined by Stanford Professor John McCarthy in 1955, was defined by him as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”.

Artificial intelligence in business is the use of AI tools such as machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision to optimize business functions, boost employee productivity, and drive business value.

2

MAIN FEATURES OF AI

- Automates repetitives tasks
- Processes large databases
- Learn from experience
- Enhance decision making

Artificial Intelligence stands out due to its ability to learn and adopt over time. It helps streamline operations and offers more accurate results than traditional methods.

Co-funded by the European Union

AI TERMINOLOGY

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.newsletter.datadrivencv.io/p/struggle-to-understand-ai-get-the>

Let's talk AI experience!

Have you ever worked on an AI/ML project?
In what context? (school, internship, hackathon, ...)

What tools or platforms have you used?
e.g. ChatGPT, Google Colab, Python,

Have you ever tried building something with AI?
What was it? What worked and what didn't?

What excites you most about using AI in business?
Automation? Creativity? Customer insights?

Co-funded by
the European Union

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DAILY LIFE

AI is Already Part of Your Day – Did You Notice?

Smartphone
face unlock

**How many
AI-powered tools have you
used today?**

(Think about phone, social media, emails, ...)

Spotify
music
recommendations

ChatGPT
text generation

**Can you identify at least
3 tools that rely on AI?**

Amazon
personalized ads

Any other examples from
your morning today?

Co-funded by
the European Union

EVERYDAY EXAMPLES AND APPLICATIONS OF AI

Co-funded by
the European Union

7

MINI-WORKSHOP

From Inspiration to Innovation - How could AI help you?

Now that we've seen several real-world AI applications...

1. Which one do you use most often without realizing it?
2. Can you think of an area where AI isn't used yet — but should be?
3. Discuss in teams how AI could improve a task or challenge in your field?
4. Share one idea

Use real-life examples or imagine your own AI tool.

Co-funded by
the European Union

8

WHY IS AI IMPORTANT FOR BUSINESS?

-
1. Better decisions
 2. Efficient and productivity gains
 3. Improved speed of business
 4. New capability and business model expansions
 5. Personalized customer services and experiences
 6. Improved services
 7. Improved monitoring
 8. Better quality and reduction of human error
 9. Better talent management
 10. More innovation
 11. Increased profitability
 12. Industry-specific improvements

Co-funded by the European Union

THE CHALLENGES OF AI IN BUSINESS

- 1** Privacy and Data Security Concerns

(Balance the power of AI with strict data privacy and security practices to protect personal information)
- 2** Understanding AI's Capabilities and Limitations

(Using it responsibly – enhancing human intelligence, not replacing it)
- 3** Ethical and Employment Considerations

(Solving problems like unfair decisions in AI and preparing workers for the future with technology.)

Co-funded by the European Union

HOW DOES ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WORK?

The AI process starts with collecting and cleaning data, transforming it into useful features, training a model, using it to make predictions, and improving it through feedback.

Co-funded by the European Union

TYPES OF AI TO PROPEL YOUR BUSINESS

Co-funded by the European Union

APPLICATIONS OF AI TOOLS IN BUSINESS

AI tools in business are applied to automate tasks, enhance decision-making, personalize customer experiences, optimize operations, and analyze data for improved efficiency and growth.

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

AI TOOLS FOR BUSINESS

Co-funded by the European Union

AI TOOLS FOR BUSINESS

Co-funded by the European Union

EXPLORING AI'S IMPACT ACROSS YOUR BUSINESS

- **Market research & Competitive analysis**

Automates data collection, trend analysis, and competitor insights to support market and competitive analysis.

- **Audience segmentation & Personalization**

Analyzes customer behaviors and preferences for more effective market segmentation and tailored offerings.

- **Financial management**

Automates financial tracking, cash flow management, and revenue forecasting, contributing to more accurate financial planning.

- **Human resources & Team management**

Supports performance analysis, recruitment forecasting, and HR automation to optimize workforce management.

- **Customer experience & Post-sales support**

Enhances customer service through AI-driven chatbots and feedback analysis for continuous product and Service improvement.

DO YOU KNOW OTHERS?

Co-funded by
the European Union

17

ChatGPT

ChatGPT (<https://chat.openai.com>)

- AI chatbot that understands and generates human-like text, answers questions, solves problems, and generates content
- Market leader in generative AI models
- ChatGPT offers
 - Internet browsing for augmented answers
 - Text-to-image generation with DALL-E
 - Supports **documents** and **images** as input

ChatGPT 4

How can I help you today?

Suggest fun activities

for a family of 4 to do indoors on a rainy day

Show me a code snippet

of a website's sticky header

Co-funded by
the European Union

18

AI THAT MATTERS, AS IT HAPPENS, IN PLAIN ENGLISH!

What does “ChatGPT” stand for, and what does “GPT” mean?

Co-funded by
the European Union

19

QUICK AI QUIZ: ARE YOU PAYING ATTENTION?

- What is the difference between ChatGPT and a Large Language Model (LLM)?
- Who developed ChatGPT and what technology is it based on?
- Can you name a few examples of LLMs other than GPT?
- What are some of the **ethical concerns** related to using LLMs like ChatGPT in education or business?
- What are some **limitations** of ChatGPT and similar Large Language Models?

Co-funded by
the European Union

20

ChatGPT CAN'T DRAW A FULL GRASS OF WINE

What's going on here?

Co-funded by
the European Union

21

PROMPT STRUCTURE

Contextⁿ, n>=1

1. Persona *Who is the AI supposed to "be" while answering?*

Helps guide tone, expertise, and perspective.

Example: "You are a senior startup advisor..."

2. Task Understanding *What is the task or problem the AI should solve?*

Clear explanation of what's expected.

Example: "Your task is to create a milestone plan for a new fintech startup..."

3. Task Recipe (Steps) *How should the AI approach the task?*

Step-by-step or logical structure.

Example: "Start by outlining major phases, then add deliverables and timelines..."

What you ask shapes what you get.

Co-funded by
the European Union

22

PROMPT STRUCTURE

Contextⁿ, n>=1

4. Guidelines

Rules, preferences, or constraints. Style, tone, content restrictions, etc.

Example: "Use professional tone, avoid buzzwords, keep each milestone under 20 words."

5. Answer Formatting *How should the output look?*

Structure: bullets, tables, sections, etc.

Example: "Present milestones in a table with columns: Phase | Milestone | Timeline | Owner."

6. Data Input *What information should the AI use?*

The raw material: text, links, user-provided context.

What you ask shapes what you get.

Co-funded by
the European Union

23

PROMPT STRUCTURE

Contextⁿ, n>=1

Example:

Persona: You are a startup consultant.

Task Understanding: Help an entrepreneur build a 6-month milestone plan.

Task Recipe: Break the plan into 3 phases, each with clear goals and deliverables.

Guidelines: Keep language clear, don't exceed 3 milestones per phase, align with lean startup principles.

Answer Formatting: Use a markdown table.

Data Input: The startup is an early-stage edtech app helping students with AI tutoring.

Suggestions to improve?

What you ask shapes what you get.

Co-funded by
the European Union

24

ITERATE YOUR PROMPT

Testⁿ, n>=1

Based on your first result, find the flaws and areas for **improvements**

1. Analyze the output
2. Identify gaps or errors

Tip: Look for hallucinations, inconsistencies, or formatting issues.

3. Refine your prompt

Tip: Be explicit - vague prompts lead to vague responses.

Tip: Find parts of your answer that you wish went into more depth and separate this into its own prompt

4. Evaluate and optimize

25

PROMPT ENGINEERING EXAMPLES

Give me a startup idea.

Summarize the main ideas in 3 concise bullet points.

I want you to write a long and really smart business idea that makes sense and people will like and that's sort of new and has something to do with AI, and could work in education or maybe in business, and explain it well.

Give me a startup idea for a mobile app.

What are the pros and cons of using AI in education?

Act as a student preparing a class presentation. List 3 pros and 3 cons of using AI tools in education. Each point should be concise, realistic, and backed by a short reason or example.

You are a startup mentor. Suggest a unique startup idea for a mobile app targeting university students who struggle with motivation in online courses. Include: the problem, the app's key features, why this idea could succeed. Respond in 3 short paragraphs.

Tell me about marketing.

26

PROMPT ENGINEERING EXAMPLES

Try advanced ChatGPT prompting
<https://www.aiforwork.co/>

How accurate and relevant were the results provided by the AI?

How easy was it to understand the reasoning behind the AI-generated results?

27

WHERE IS THE FOCUS NOW? AGENTIC WORKFLOWS

28

IdeaMap

IdeaMap (<https://ideamap.ai>)

- An AI-powered brainstorming and mind mapping tool designed to enhance creativity and productivity for individuals and teams.
- Features:
 - AI-assisted **idea generation**
 - Customizable templates
 - Real-time collaboration
 - Dynamic idea organization
 - Allows users to visualize and structure their thoughts effectively

Where **ideas and AI** come together.

Empower your team to brainstorm better and faster with Ideamap

Describe your challenge...

Brainstorm →

Co-funded by the European Union

29

IdeaBuddy

IdeaBuddy (<https://ideabuddy.com>)

- All-in-one business planning software designed to guide entrepreneurs and startups through every stage of their business journey, from initial concept to execution.
- Functionalities:
 - Business **idea generation**
 - Idea viability assessment
 - Scenario analysis and forecasting
 - Support for business plan development
 - Market analysis and trend identification

Idea Purpose
Product & Service

Create high quality ideas based on a goal-driven idea collection with the help of Ideanote's trained AI.

Company or Project Name
ACME Inc.

Company or Project Summary
X project was founded in x and is known fo...

Generate Ideas

ADVANCED
COMPANY PROFILE
AI SETTINGS

Welcome to the AI Idea Generator
Fill in some information about your company and click generate.

Co-funded by the European Union

30

Ideogram.AI

Ideogram.ai (<https://ideogram.ai/>)

- A free AI tool that turns ideas into realistic images, innovative **logos and posters**.
- Functionalities:
 - Various style presets
 - Detail the content of an image
 - Adjusting aspect ratio and resolution:
 - Uploading and editing images
 - Combine images and previous requests to create new variations.
 - Generate private images

Co-funded by
the European Union

QuickBooks

QuickBooks (<https://quickbooks.intuit.com/eu/>)

- QuickBooks AI uses machine learning to **analyze financial data** and make accurate financial forecasts.
- Features:
 - Generate financial projections
 - Budget tracking
 - Automate accounting processes
 - Generate customized financial reports
 - Performance analysis

Co-funded by
the European Union

Tableau

Tableau (<https://www.tableau.com>)

- Tableau AI-driven features focus on simplifying data analysis through **automated insights, predictive analytics, and intelligent recommendations.**
- Key capabilities include:
 - Smart Data Preparation
 - AI-Powered Insights
 - Natural Language Processing
 - Predictive Analytics

Co-funded by
the European Union

33

Pitching I

Your slides and presentation should address the following:

- Clear articulation of the **idea**
- What **problem** does it solve?
- How does it **work**?
- What **resources** are needed to implement?
- How will you **acquire** the resources?
- What **value** does it bring to the market?
- What's your **first actionable step**?

Other notes

- Team pitches
- 10 minutes presentation with 3-4 minutes of Q&A

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pitching II

- Evaluate if your chosen **business idea** can be optimized (quick brainstorm using ChatGPT and/or IdeaMap)
- Generate a **brand name** for your business (using ChatGPT or/and Business Name Generator)
- Design a **company logo** (using an Ideogram.ai)
- Review and improve your **business plan** using AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, IdeaBuddy, or LivePlan) to enhance clarity, feasibility, and impact.
- Write a creative **social media post** to promote your business

Co-funded by
the European Union

35

RESOURCES

- <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/10-examples-of-artificial-intelligence-in-real-life-2024/>
- <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/feature/6-key-benefits-of-AI-for-business>
- <https://adamfard.com/blog/impact-of-ai-in-business>
- <https://www.theknowledgeacademy.com/blog/what-is-artificial-intelligence-ai/>
- <https://adamfard.com/blog/ai-in-business-operation>
- <https://www.newsletter.datadrivencvc.io/p/struggle-to-understand-ai-get-the>
- <https://www.reddit.com/>
- <https://cobusgreyling.medium.com/why-the-focus-has-shifted-from-ai-agents-to-agentic-workflows-51e4078d03c2>

Co-funded by
the European Union

36

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME AND ATTENTION

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universitatea
Transilvania
din Braşov

Research Project Management

Mihai IVANOVICI

10 April 2025

1

Overview

- Rationale – entrepreneur vs. manager
- Context – be aware of strategies
- How to approach the problem
- Resources – how to implement your project
- Project components – how to write the project proposal
- Usefull advices

Co-funded by
the European Union

2

Preamble

„At this point in your career, your only possible promotion is to management, where you will stop doing the work you love and use a skill set you don't have and we don't teach”

Co-funded by
the European Union

3

What is research?

Research

definitions from Merriam-Webster Dictionary

- 1: careful or diligent search
- 2: studious inquiry or examination
 - *especially*: investigation or experimentation aimed at the discovery and interpretation of facts, revision of accepted theories or laws in the light of new facts, or practical application of such new or revised theories or laws
- 3: the collecting of information about a particular subject

Co-funded by
the European Union

4

What is research?

The idea is
volatile!

Co-funded by
the European Union

5

Taxonomy

- Fundamental and applicative research
- Multi- or inter-disciplinary research
- Scientific research domains [*must be specified in the call / proposal*]:
 - ...
 - **Electronics and telecommunications engineering**
 - Computers and Information Technology
 - Computer Science
 - Mathematics
 - ...

Co-funded by
the European Union

6

Who is doing research?

- Anyone can do research! 😊
- Researchers from
 - R & D Institutes
 - Universities
 - Private companies
 - Army
 - ...
- Pay attention to the eligibility criteria – e.g. for the Principal Investigator (may be *you*), team members and/or the institution

Co-funded by
the European Union

7

Why we do research?

- Knowledge-based society
- Society/humanity's progress is based on research
- For fun... or fame
- To foster/capitalize the scientific research results
 - Protection of Intellectual Property
- To answer to a specific call (Call for Proposals, e.g. Horizon Europe calls)
 - Increasing the visibility of Romanian scientific research

Co-funded by
the European Union

8

Who finances research and why?

- Financing sources for scientific research
 - Government/Ministry of Education and/or Research
 - In Romania: UEFISCDI – <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/>
 - Private companies
 - Army / NATO
 - NGOs
 - etc

Co-funded by
the European Union

9

A framework for research

- Within a research project
- Research project lifetime:

Co-funded by
the European Union

10

Public financing

Co-funded by the European Union

howmuch.net

Research strategies

- Who elaborates these strategies?
- European Commission
- Government / Ministry of Education and/or Research
- <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/strategia-cdi-2014-2020>
- Regional Growing Agency
 - See the Smart Specialization Strategy
 - <http://www.adrcentru.ro/dezvoltare-regionala-cat/strategia-de-specializare-inteligenta/>
- City Hall / County Hall
 - https://site.judbrasov.ro/page_Stategia-de-dezvoltare-durabil-a-jude-ului-Bra-ov_57.html

Co-funded by the European Union

Programs, objectives and financing instruments (UEFISCDI)

- P1 – Development of the R&D national system
 - 1.1 Human resources
 - 1.2 Institutional excellence
 - 1.3 R & D Infrastructures
 - 1.4 Support
- P2 – Increasing the competitiveness of the Romanian economy through Research, Development and Innovation
 - 2.1 Competitiveness through research, development and innovation
- P3 – European and international cooperation
 - 3.1 Bilateral/multi-lateral
 - 3.2 Horizon 2020
 - 3.3 Other European and international initiatives
 - 3.4 Support
- P4 – Fundamental / frontier research

Co-funded by
the European Union

13

EC Funding & Tenders Portal

European Commission | EU Funding & Tenders Portal

Discover the funding & tenders opportunities

Find out how to participate by following these key steps.

- Find calls for proposals**
Explore the available EU funding opportunities by searching for calls for proposals within your topics of interest, find partners and submit a proposal.
- Find calls for tenders
Find business opportunities in the calls for tenders managed by EU institutions, bodies and agencies.
- View projects and results
Browse through EU funded projects and learn about the results. Invest in opportunities and get inspired by the highlights and success stories.
- Work as an expert
Proposals and projects need evaluations, monitoring and domain-specific knowledge advice from experts.

Report fraud

14

Calls for project proposals

The screenshot shows the 'Calls for proposals' page on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal. The page title is 'Calls for proposals' and it includes a brief description: 'Calls for proposals are funding opportunities issued by the European Union institutions, agencies and bodies. These are direct financial contributions, known as grants, that are awarded to third-party beneficiaries (e.g., research organisations, public entities, non-governmental organisations, and private companies) to engage in activities that serve EU policies.' Below this, there are filters for '121 item(s) found' and a 'Quick search' bar. A list of three calls for proposals is displayed, each with a 'Forthcoming' status:

- European Researchers' Night and Researchers at Schools 2026-2027**
HORIZON-MSCA-2025-CITIZENS-01-01 | Call for proposal
Opening date: 17 June 2025 | Next deadline: 22 October 2025 | Single-stage
Programme: **Horizon Europe (HORIZON)** | Type of action: **HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions**
- MSCA COFUND 2025**
HORIZON-MSCA-2025-COFUND-01-01 | Call for proposal
Opening date: 23 January 2025 | Next deadline: 24 June 2025 | Single-stage
Programme: **Horizon Europe (HORIZON)** | Type of action: **HORIZON TMA MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral programme**
- Teaming for Excellence**
HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ACCESS-01-01-two-stage | Call for proposal
Opening date: 03 December 2024 | Next deadline: 10 April 2025 | Two-stage
Programme: **Horizon Europe (HORIZON)** | Type of action: **HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions**

15

A random example

The screenshot shows the details page for the 'MSCA Staff Exchanges 2024' call for proposal (HORIZON-MSCA-2024-SE-01-01). The page includes an 'Internal navigation' sidebar and a main content area with the following information:

- General information**
 - Programme: Horizon Europe (HORIZON) [Budget overview]
 - Call: MSCA Staff Exchanges 2024 (HORIZON-MSCA-2024-SE-01)
 - Type of action: HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-SE HORIZON TMA MSCA Staff Exchanges | Type of MGA: HORIZON Unit Grant [HORIZON-AG-UN] [Open For Submission]
 - Deadline model: single-stage | Opening date: 19 September 2024 | Deadline date: 05 February 2025 17:00:00 Brussels time
- Topic description**
 - Expected Outcome: Project results are expected to contribute to the following outcomes:
For staff members...
 - [Show more]

16

Decoding the call

EU Funding & Tenders Portal

Home Funding Procurement Projects & results News & events Work as an expert Guidance & documents

Start submission

Topic Q&As
Get support
Call information
Call updates

Topic description

Expected Outcome:
Project results are expected to contribute to the following outcomes:

For staff members

- Increased set of research and transferable skills and competences, leading to improved employability and career prospects within and outside academia;
- More knowledge and innovative ideas converted into products, processes and services;
- More entrepreneurial mind-sets, testing new and innovative ideas;
- Increased international exposure leading to extended networks and opportunities;
- Enhanced networking and communication capacities with scientific peers, as well as with the general public that will increase and broaden the research and innovation impact.

For participating organisations

- Innovative ways of cooperation and transfer of knowledge between sectors and disciplines;
- Strengthened and broader international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaborative networks;
- Boosted R&I capacity.

Scope:

MSCA Staff Exchanges involve organisations from the academic and non-academic sectors (including SMEs) from across the globe.
Support is provided for international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary mobility of R&I staff leading to knowledge transfer between participating organisations.

Mobility through secondments

The organisations constituting the partnership contribute directly to the implementation of a joint R&I project by seconding and/or hosting eligible staff members. Such a

17

Next step

EU Funding & Tenders Portal

Home Funding Procurement Projects & results News & events Work as an expert Guidance & documents

Start submission

Topic Q&As
Get support
Call information
Call updates

Topic description

Expected Outcome:
Project results are expected to contribute to the following outcomes:

For staff members

- Increased set of research and transferable skills and competences, leading to improved employability and career prospects within and outside academia;
- More knowledge and innovative ideas converted into products, processes and services;
- More entrepreneurial mind-sets, testing new and innovative ideas;
- Increased international exposure leading to extended networks and opportunities;
- Enhanced networking and communication capacities with scientific peers, as well as with the general public that will increase and broaden the research and innovation impact.

For participating organisations

- Innovative ways of cooperation and transfer of knowledge between sectors and disciplines;
- Strengthened and broader international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaborative networks;
- Boosted R&I capacity.

Scope:

MSCA Staff Exchanges involve organisations from the academic and non-academic sectors (including SMEs) from across the globe.
Support is provided for international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary mobility of R&I staff leading to knowledge transfer between participating organisations.

Mobility through secondments

The organisations constituting the partnership contribute directly to the implementation of a joint R&I project by seconding and/or hosting eligible staff members. Such a

18

A useful ... triptych

Co-funded by
the European Union

19

The typical structure

Co-funded by
the European Union

20

The goal (of the project)

- Or the aim – what do I wish to do / obtain by the end of the project?
- The goal must correlate to the goal of the competition
 - *And not only!* – to the European/national/institutional strategy

Project goal	Competition goal
I wish to relax and have fun! (bad example)	e.g. PN-III-DCD-RU-PD-2019-2 - Support young researchers who wish to develop a professional career in scientific research, in R&D institutions in Romania.

Co-funded by
the European Union

21

Good example – PED 2019 Call

- **Project scope:** to design, implement, validate and test a fully-functional experimental demonstrative model of an Augmented Reality product (both a hardware system and the associate software application) based on multi-spectral imaging technology and multispectral image analysis techniques, for the intelligent specialization domain of *Information and Communication Technologies* with application in the public domain of *Cultural Heritage and Identity*. More specifically, we aim to design, implement, test and validate a hardware and software product based on AR intelligent glasses enabling the examination of cultural heritage artefacts by means of multispectral imaging technologies and multispectral image analysis techniques, to be used either by specialists in Cultural Heritage or visitors in museums for the identifications of elements of interest in various spectral bandwidths (i.e. specific wavelength intervals) like specific materials and pigments, defects or anomalies, presence of underlying or newly-added layers which are not visible to the naked or unexperienced human eye etc.

Co-funded by
the European Union

22

Project objectives

- What do I do to reach my project goal/target?
- Objectives must lead clearly and evidently to reaching project target and must be correlated to the competition's objectives

Project objectives	Competition objectives (PN-III-DCD-RU-PD-2019-2)
Research results dissemination (publication of <i>N</i> scientific articles in international peer-review journals with impact factor)	<u>Increasing the visibility of Romanian research at international level</u>

Co-funded by
the European Union

23

Participation conditions PED 2019 call

- Project proposals must fall within the following situations:
 - Start from a technology/product concept (TRL 2) and reach an in-lab experimental demonstrator (TRL 3);
 - Start from an in-lab experimental demonstrator (TRL 3) and reach an in-lab validated technology (TRL 4);
 - Start from a technology/product concept (TRL 2) and reach an in-lab validated technology (TRL 4).

Co-funded by
the European Union

24

Participation conditions PED 2019 call

Project proposals must be elaborated in the following domains/subdomains:

- Smart specialization domains:
 - Bioeconomy
 - Information technology and communications (ITC):
 - Space
 - Security
 - Energy, environment and [climate changes](#)
 - Eco-nano-technologies and advanced materials
- Public priority domains:
 - Health
 - Cultural Heritage and Identity:
 - Cultural Heritage
 - Cultural Identity

Co-funded by
the European Union

25

Objectives – examples PED 2019 call

Transversal Objective (TO)	to use and foster the acquired knowledge in the fundamental research in multispectral imaging and multispectral image analysis of the project coordinator (TRL 2) for integrating it in a superior technological level i.e. an in-laboratory validated technology (TRL 4) and to grow the capacity of the project coordinator to generate technical solutions validated in laboratory for AR systems/applications/products and offer them to the project partner (company)
Scientific Objective (SO)	to design, implement, validate and test a multispectral imaging system, a set of real-time multispectral image analysis approaches and augmented reality tools that allows reaching the scope of the ARCHES project, i.e. the ARCHES system and application
Dissemination Objective (DO)	to increase the visibility of the MIV research laboratory through participation in international conferences and publication in international journals with high impact factor
IP Protection Objective (PO)	to identify, protect and capitalize new scientific findings of the ARCHES project that have the potential of being technologically applicable and valorized through means of intellectual property protection
Management Objective (MO)	to ensure the appropriate project management that leads to a successful implementation of the ARCHES project

Co-funded by
the European Union

26

How do I implement the project?

Types of resources

- Human resources
 - Researchers / professors
- Material resources
 - Research infrastructure
 - Financement (project budget)
- Informational resources
 - Access to scientific literature
- Other resources
 - Intellectual Property (e.g. patents)
 - Technologies

Co-funded by
the European Union

27

Human resource in research activity

- Researchers (R&D Institutes)
 - Scientific researchers (I, II, III) & research assistant
 - Technological development engineer (I, II, III)
 - Technician
- Teaching staff
 - Professor
 - Assistant professor
 - Lecturer
 - Teaching assistant

Co-funded by
the European Union

28

Costs (Romanian example) HG nr. 751 / 2017

Activities	Position	Hourly fee
High level of creativity and/or experience and management abilities	Professor and assistant professor, manager, scientific researcher (type I or II)...	225 RON/h
Deep understanding of analysis and synthesis methods and abilities of using them	Lecturer, researcher, post-doctoral student ...	157 RON/h
Understanding of analysis and synthesis methods and research methodology and abilities of using them	Research assistant, PhD student...	112 RON/h
Support activities	Technician ...	67 RON/h

Co-funded by the European Union

29

The Man-Month Concept

- Man-Month (MM) or Person-Month (PM)
- $1 \text{ PM} = \text{no. hours per month} * \text{hourly fee}$
- E.g. a researcher can do 1 full time norm (maximum 168 h/month) according to the contract
- Example: $1 \text{ PM (prof.)} = 160 \text{ h/month} * 230 \text{ lei/h} = 36,8 \text{ klei/month}$
- Project implication can be *fractional*
 - $0.2 \text{ PM} = 20\% \text{ FTE} = 32 \text{ h / month}$

Co-funded by the European Union

30

Project team / roles

- Adapted to the size and specificity of the project
 - 1 PhD student + 1 Mentor
 - 1 Post-doctoral student + 1 Mentor (POST-DOC)
 - 2-3 PhD students, 1-2 post-doc student(s), 1 mentor
 - PhD students, post-docs, junior researchers, senior researchers, „principal investigator“, project manager/responsible, scientific committee, advisory board...
- Brain Map Platform: <https://www.brainmap.ro/>

Co-funded by
the European Union

31

Research infrastructure

- Research laboratory equipment
- Large research infrastructures
 - LHC, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland (ATLAS Experiment)
 - ELI, IFIN-HH, Măgurele, Romania
 - Danube Delta, Romania
- ERRIS Platform - <https://erris.gov.ro/>

Co-funded by
the European Union

32

Financial resources

- Project budget
 - Integral – from European funds
 - Co-financing (from the institution which implements the project, if the case)
 - Must be correlated to the eligible costs (see the information package / applicant guide for the call)
 - Direct costs (salaries) and other direct costs
 - Equipment / Logistics
 - Indirect costs (overhead)
- Own/institutional funds
- Other financial resources
 - **Avoid double financing!**

Co-funded by
the European Union

33

Project budget

- Direct costs (salaries)
 - correlated to the implementation team and the project activities
- Equipment
 - correlated to the infrastructure and the project activities
- Mobilities
 - Correlated to the project activities (meetings) and dissemination plan (participation to international conferences) and communication (events)
- Indirect costs (overhead)
 - Usually specified by the call (e.g. 25% of the total budget) or by the institution (e.g. 18% of direct costs)

Co-funded by
the European Union

34

Project implementation plan

- Mean defining / specifying:
 - Research project components
 - Project phases and milestones
 - Work packages – correlated to the project goal and objectives
 - Tasks – correlated to project objectives
 - Deliverables – every task/activity must have at least one deliverable
 - Risk analysis and mitigation
 - Management plant – coordination, monitoring and reporting
 - Consortium (if the case)

Co-funded by
the European Union

35

Research project components

- Scientific Research
- Dissemination and Communication
- IP Protection
- Human Resource
- Acquisition
- Management*

* Sometimes can be not eligible, thus not financed.

Co-funded by
the European Union

36

PERT Chart

PERT – Project Evaluation Review Technique

Co-funded by the European Union

PERT Chart (2)

Source:

Sean McCarthy, *How to write a competitive proposal for Horizon 2020 – A Research Manager’s Handbook*, Hyperion Ltd., 2013

Co-funded by the European Union

Gantt Diagram

Co-funded by the European Union

Gantt Diagram (2)

Source:

Sean McCarthy, *How to write a competitive proposal for Horizon 2020 – A Research Manager’s Handbook*, Hyperion Ltd., 2013

Co-funded by the European Union

Milestones - examples

- **MS1** at Month 12, the successful implementation of the multispectral imaging system
- **MS2** at Month 12, the successful implementation of all the hardware and software components of the ARCHES system and application and the elaboration of the complete specifications for the experimental demonstrator, finally
- **MS3** at Month 19 the successful in-lab validation of the proposed ARCHES system and application experimental demonstrator.

Co-funded by
the European Union

41

Deliverables

- Activity reports
- Design/implementation specifications
- Algorithms and software implementation (applications, libraries)
- Hardware implementations (PCB, ASIC/FPGA)
- Validation/test report
- Scientific publications
- Report on dissemination/communication events
- Etc.

Co-funded by
the European Union

42

Deliverables - examples

No.	Type	Description	Delivery date
D1.1	Report	Report containing the requirements of the ARCHES system and application and updated state-of-the-art on the existing solutions	Month 1
D1.2	Report, Data	Report containing the specifications of the multispectral imaging component of ARCHES system and a set of labelled multispectral images of cultural heritage artefacts	Month 6
D1.3	Report	Report containing the specifications of the multispectral image feature extraction software component of ARCHES application	Month 12
D4.1	Report	Monthly synthetic internal report on the activity of CO and P1	Every month
D4.2	Report	Yearly scientific/technical and financial report to financing body	Month 8, 20, 24

Co-funded by the European Union

Work Package description

Table 3.1a Work Package Description	
Work Package No	Start date or starting event:
Work Package Title	
Participant Number	
Person-months per participant	
Objectives	
Description of Work (where appropriate, broken down into tasks), lead partner and role of participants	
Deliverables (Brief description and month of delivery)	

Source:

Sean McCarthy, *How to write a competitive proposal for Horizon 2020 – A Research Manager’s Handbook*, Hyperion Ltd., 2013

Co-funded by the European Union

Risk analysis

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation
The scientific articles are not accepted for publication in the envisaged international journals from Q1 (red zone).	Low	Delay in delivering D2.1a and D2.1b	The scientific articles will be resubmitted to international journals in Q2 (yellow zone).
There will be no findings potentially being protected as a patent, as they are not related to technological processes	Low / Medium	No D3.1	A scientific paper will be written instead of a patent proposal
The work is delayed and the estimated results of the project are not delivered on time	Low	Delay in delivering D4.1 and D4.2	The project will be monitored in terms of activities and their outcomes on a monthly basis
One of the partners leaves the consortium	Very low	May affect all deliverables	Both partners are sound institutions, eligible for the call, with strong intentions to implement the ARCHES project

Co-funded by the European Union

45

Project budget

Allocated budget / costs (euro)						
		Personal costs	Logistics	Travel	Indirect costs	Total
Coordinator (CO)	Public budget	252.000	30.000	12.000	66.000	360.000
	Partner 1	192.000	0	0	48.000	240.000
	Own contribution	73.728	0	20.000	23.432	117.160
Total		517.728	30.000	32.000	137.432	717.160

Co-funded by the European Union

46

Project management

- Project Management: Project management is the process of matching a project's goals, tasks, resources to accomplish a goal as needed.
- Project lifecycle: the path linking the idea with the final set of results

Co-funded by
the European Union

47

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

- TRL is a concept that was developed in the Space and Aeronautics industries
- It is now used in most technology sectors to describe the state of development of a technology
- Several definition of TRL exist
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-FLa3lfJkNo>

Co-funded by
the European Union

48

TRL – OECD Definition (Horizon 2020)

TRL 1	basic principles observed
TRL 2	technology concept formulated
TRL 3	experimental proof of concept
TRL 4	technology validated in lab
TRL 5	technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6	technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7	system prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL 8	system complete and qualified
TRL 9	actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

Co-funded by
the European Union

NASA TRL

Co-funded by
the European Union

Discussion

Valley of Death – between TRL 3 and 6

„almost ready” ≠ ready

Source:

Sean McCarthy, *How to write a competitive proposal for Horizon 2020 – A Research Manager’s Handbook*, Hyperion Ltd., 2013

Co-funded by the European Union

Risk vs. Value (as a function of TRL)

Co-funded by the European Union

Graphical abstract

- Definition: graphical or visual abstract is graphical equivalent of a written abstract
- Realization: graphical abstract is a single image designed to help the reader to quickly get an overview of the project
- Can have the purpose of attracting the attention of the reader

Co-funded by
the European Union

53

Elsevier definition on graphical abstract

- <https://www.elsevier.com/authors/journal-authors/graphical-abstract>
- A graphical abstract is a single, concise, pictorial and visual summary of the main findings of the article. This could either be the concluding figure from the article or a figure that is specially designed for the purpose, which captures the content of the article for readers at a single glance.
- A graphical abstract should allow readers to quickly gain an understanding of the main take-home message of the paper and is intended to encourage browsing, promote interdisciplinary scholarship, and help readers identify more quickly which papers are most relevant to their research interests.

Co-funded by
the European Union

54

Exemples (from Elsevier)

Co-funded by
the European Union

55

Types of graphical abstracts

One can distinguish the following 4 styles / types:

- Diagram type/style
- Visual summary type/style
- Infographic type/style
- Comic type/style

Co-funded by
the European Union

56

Diagram style

Co-funded by the European Union

57

Infographic style

Co-funded by the European Union

58

Comic style

Co-funded by
the European Union

59

Other graphical elements: Logo

- A graphical symbol to identify a research project
- Can be designed based on the project acronym

ARCHES - Augmented Reality System
and Application for Cultural Heritage Examination
using Multi-Spectral Imaging Technologies

Co-funded by
the European Union

60

Logos - examples

COMET - Microelectronics and computing for space applications

VIPERA – Versatile Imaging Platform for Emerging Reconfigurable Applications

Expanding the participation of Romania within Copernicus by increasing research excellence in ARTificial Intelligence for rEmote Sensing applications

Co-funded by the European Union

61

Collaborative context of project consortium

Co-funded by the European Union

62

Methodology

Figure 5. Methodology for training and mentoring during ARIES.

Dissemination & communication

Consortium – partners and domains of expertise

Co-funded by the European Union

65

Consortium – management structure

Co-funded by the European Union

66

Data Management Plan

- How you handle the data (create, store, distribute etc.)?
- Where do you store your data? Platforms
- Who has access to your data?

Co-funded by
the European Union

67

Open Science at a glance

- Open Data
- Open Material
- Open Access
- Open Source (software)
- Open Peer Review
- Open Educational Resources

Co-funded by
the European Union

68

Open Science Taxonomy

Pontika N, Knoth P, Cancellieri M, et al.: Fostering Open Science to Research Using a Taxonomy and an ELearning Portal. In Proceedings of the 15th Intl. Conf. on Knowledge Technologies and Data-Driven Business - i-KNOW 15. ACM. 2015. 69

Co-funded by the European Union

Why Open Science?

- aims at transforming science through digital tools and networks, to make research more open, global, collaborative, creative and closer to society
- is about the way research is carried out, disseminated, deployed and transformed by digital tools and networks
- makes scientific processes more efficient, transparent and responsive to societal challenges by providing **open access** to research outputs

Co-funded by the European Union

A European Strategy for Open Science

- https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science_en
- EC launched the "European Cloud Initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe" to endorse Open science.
- Through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), researchers will
 - be able to **process huge amounts of scientific data** and
 - **share their scientific results** while improving access to knowledge and, consequently, to innovation

Co-funded by
the European Union

71

Co-funded by
the European Union

Source: The Open Science Training Handbook <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1212496>⁷²

Co-funded by the European Union

Source: The Open Science Training Handbook <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1212496>⁷³

Two sides of the same coin

Open = Sharing	Closed = Secrecy
Scientific skepticism	Scientific dogmatism
Universality of results	Particularity of results
Evaluate research on own merit	Evaluate research on reputation
Motivated by knowledge & discovery	Treat science as a competition
Value reproducibility (quality)	Value # of published papers (quantity*)

*Publish or perish!

Co-funded by the European Union

74

A published article is...

- ...just the tip of the iceberg!
- “An article (about computational result) is advertising, not scholarship. The actual scholarship is the full software environment, code and data, that produced the result.”
 - Buckheit and Donoho (1995)
- The open science equation:

Open science = article + data + code

Co-funded by
the European Union

75

Open Data? Yes, please

- Definition: *Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone*
 - <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/what-is-open-data/>
- Enables new research methods
- Allows for the engagement of the society
- Offers open access to research
- Supports collaboration and sharing in research

Co-funded by
the European Union

76

Open Data Context

Based on: https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/sites/digital-agenda/files/DS_6_0.png

Co-funded by the European Union

Open data enables reproducibility

		Data	
		Same	Different
Analysis	Same	Reproducible	Replicable
	Different	Robust	Generalisable

Co-funded by the European Union

Open Data Attributes

- Availability and Access:
 - data must be available ..., preferably by downloading over the internet
 - data must also be available in a convenient and modifiable form
- Re-use and Redistribution
 - data must be provided under terms that permit re-use and redistribution including the intermixing with other datasets.
- Universal Participation
 - everyone must be able to use, re-use and redistribute

Co-funded by
the European Union

79

Intellectual Property

- Back to the goal of research...
- IP rights (IPR) protection through patenting
- A way to foster the project results and return investment*
- Check IP bodies: EPO, WIPO etc.
- Patent request – both **legal** and **technical** document
- Inventorship vs. ownership

Co-funded by
the European Union

80

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universitatea
Transilvania
din Braşov

Human Skills for Entrepreneurs

Mihaela VOINEA

10 April 2025

Milestones/Objectives:

- To explain the differences between hard-soft-human skills;
- To identify one's most critical soft skills/human skills in contemporary society;
- To evaluate the importance of human skills for business.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Our Group Rules (ASK):

1. Be critical thinkers: **ASK!**
2. Be ready to share the experiences: **Share with us!**
3. Be nice and respectful: **Kindness!**

Co-funded by
the European Union

Reflection: Hard –Soft –Human Skills in digitalized society

Co-funded by
the European Union

Why Human skills and not Soft skills?

Act, Think & Communicate from the *INSIDE* OUT!

WHY - Your Purpose

Your motivation? What do you believe?

HOW - Your Process

Specific actions taken to realize your Why

WHAT - Your Result

What do you do? The result of Why. Proof

Co-funded by
the European Union

Soft Skills or **Human Skills**?

- In the future, in an uncertain world, people (who are students now) need **mental flexibility and emotional balance** because we don't want to be "**downgraded people** who use wrong **upgraded computers** with devastating effects on themselves and the world"(Harari, 2018, p.82)

„The future may be uncertain, but by equipping the next generation with **these essential skills**, one thing is certain: **they will be ready to meet it.**“(Andreas Schleicher, OECD, 2024)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Reflection: Soft Skills or **Human Skills**?

- ▣ **Open mindedness** (curiosity, tolerance, creativity)
- ▣ **Task performance** (responsibility, self-control, persistence, achievement motivation)
- ▣ **Engaging with others** (sociability, assertiveness, energy)
- ▣ **Collaboration** (empathy, trust)
- ▣ **Emotional regulation** (stress resilience, optimism, emotional control)- OECD,2024

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Conclusion:

- Soft skills/ human skills are **personal attributes** that enable individuals **to interact effectively and harmoniously** with others.
- Social competences are being redefined according to social trends – a new social ethic: **emphasis on mental health, inclusion and diversity, fluid identities, and a shift towards authenticity and vulnerability.**
- The social competences/ soft skills will be defined through the capacity **to balance dilemmas, find innovative solutions for people and harmonize different trends.**

Co-funded by
the European Union

Human skills for entrepreneurs

- ▣ Analyze, in groups of four, the profiles/descriptions of the people below and identify their human traits.
- ▣ Choose the person who has the profile of an entrepreneur and justify your choice.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Person A: Andrew

- Andrew is a young entrepreneur who graduated from high school with a tourism major. His childhood dream was to own a travel agency. Although he came from an ordinary family that supported his decisions, Andrew did not go to college. He preferred to "go out into the world" to learn from experience.
- He visited many European countries and worked in France, Germany and Italy for 5 years in the field of tourism.
- His bosses appreciated his collaboration skills, adaptability and initiative.
- In spite of all the difficulties, he did not forget his dream and managed to save enough money to start his dream business.
- Thanks to the contacts he made, he found a partner in Germany and Italy.
- He still needs to borrow additional money from the bank.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Person B: Barbara

- Barbara at only 25 is the owner of a gym.
- Because she had been passionate about business since childhood but also loved sports, she managed to graduate from a sports college and earn a master's degree in business management.
- Her parents supported her passion for business and gave her the opportunity to learn about it by employing her in their company.
- Barbara stood out for her strong relationships with the company's employees, her negotiation skills and her ability to influence them. When she left for her own job some of the employees followed her.
- She likes to envision different scenarios and believes that the future should be welcomed with open arms. She thinks that sports will always be a successful business, which is why she wants to expand and will apply for a loan from the bank.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Person C: Cornel

- Cornel, 45 years old, describes himself as an "experienced entrepreneur" as he has many businesses under his belt. He remembers the first one he started in his early twenties with his father's money. The business flourished quickly and then went bankrupt.
- He didn't get discouraged and started another one using the experience from the first one, but this venture didn't last long either. When he realized it wasn't working, he sold it. He then realized he needed to pay more attention to market demands, so he started talking to other entrepreneurs, took a business skills course and launched a new business.
- He is confident that this time he will succeed because he has faith in his abilities and in the collaborations with the investors he has met.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Person D: Dana

- Dana has worked for 20 years in IT at an international IT company. She has distinguished herself through her organizational and planning skills, strong relationships with colleagues of different nationalities and creativity. Now that the company has closed, Dana is considering starting her own business based on her IT experience.
- She wants to hire two highly skilled professionals in project management and marketing to help her invest and develop the business.
- She believes that a successful business is based on a team.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Conclusion:

- “Skills beget Skills” (OECD, 2015,p.74)
- Social skills/ Human skills are transferable and optimizable.
- Social skills are the useful tools for future adaptation.

Figure 4.1. Skills beget skills

Co-funded by
the European Union

A final thought

Keep human! Stay mindedness ! Be entrepreneurial!

Co-funded by
the European Union

Soft skills for entrepreneurs (II) for trainers

Co-funded by
the European Union

Objectives:

- To design training activities that develop soft skills for entrepreneurs;
- To apply effective strategies for developing soft skills for entrepreneurs in a specific context;
- To evaluate the importance of soft skills for business.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contents:

- Design training activities for soft skills: tips and tricks
- Strategies for develop soft skills in a specific context
- Assessment of soft skills

Co-funded by
the European Union

Participants:

- Take into account the inner differences among cultural backgrounds;
- Consider cultural differences;
- Recognize and respect the diversity

- Incorporating various cultural backgrounds, beliefs and experiences within resources, tasks and activities.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Promote a culture of entrepreneurship in your didactic activities!

- Ice-breaking activities;
- Establish clear communication;
- Encourage active participation from all students.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Learning outcomes

- Entrepreneurs Competencies
- Openness and respect
- Critical thinking and empathy
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Collaboration and teamwork

Co-funded by
the European Union

Learning strategies

- use **student-centered methods** in accordance with the theoretical framework chosen for competence training (case studies, reflections, debates, group-projects).
- use **'the power of group'** for learning in different social contexts.
- value **the experience of the participants**.
- Use several teaching aids: animation, multimedia resources, simulation, texts, papers, books.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Formative assessment strategies

- Quizzes
- Peer evaluations
- Self-assessment
- Group presentations

Co-funded by
the European Union

Key recommendations for improving policies and practices to better promote socio-emotional learning (OECD,2024)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Key recommendations for improving policies and practices to better promote socio-emotional learning (OECD,2024)

- ▣ Enhance teacher feedback, particularly on students' strengths
- ▣ Increase the opportunities teachers provide for social and emotional learning:
- ▣ Leverage digital technologies
- ▣ Boost teacher preparedness
- ▣ Create structures and mindsets that promote social and emotional learning
- ▣ Support extra-curricular activities

Co-funded by
the European Union

Let`s practice:

Analyze the project below and identify:

- The theoretical framework
- The type of didactic strategy
- The assessment strategy

Co-funded by
the European Union

A final thought

Keep enthusiastic! Stay realistic! Be a trainer!

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universitatea
Transilvania
din Braşov

Team management: building and managing teams

Daniela-Veronica Necşoi

11 April 2025

Objectives:

The participants will be able to:

- analyse the main characteristics of teams;
- understand the difference between teams and workgroups;
- differentiate between work situations that require teamwork and those that do not;
- analyse different types of work teams;
- analyse the stages a team goes through to improve its performance;
- analyse different processes and behaviours from each stage of team development;
- analyse some tools leaders can use to help the team develop.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Points of discussion:

- 1 What is a team? Team definition and team characteristics
- 2 The difference between a team and a working group
- 3 When and why do we need teams?
- 4 Types of teams
- 5 The stages of team development

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity: *The mascot drawing*. Instructions

- The participants are grouped into teams of 6 members.
- Each team receives an A3 sheet, a marker tied with 6 strings, and a small picture of a mascot.
- Each team must reproduce the mascot in a larger size than the one received.
- In 3 minutes, the teams need to choose a leader and develop a strategy on how to draw the mascot.
- After the 3 minutes they are not allowed to talk to each other, only the leader is allowed to talk and give instructions. In maximum 7 minutes the team must draw the mascot.
- At the end, the participants will vote for the most successful drawing.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity: *The mascot drawing. Debriefing*

- Are you satisfied with the result? Why? Why not?
- How did you choose your leader?
- What was your strategy to draw the mascot?
- What skills were needed to complete the task?
- What do you think was the key to your success? or
- What do you think were the reasons why you failed to complete the task?

Co-funded by
the European Union

1. What is a team? Team definition and team characteristics

- A team is a small number of people with **complementary skills** who are **committed to a common purpose**, set of **performance goals**, and approach for which they hold themselves **mutually accountable**.

(Katzenbach & Smith, 1993, 2005)

4 key attributes:

- Complementary skills
- Commitment to a common purpose
- Shared performance goals
- Mutual accountability

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a team?

TEAM SIZE (GUIDE)				
	Under 5	6-12	13-15	15+
Problem solving	3	2	1	4
Speed of judgements	1	2	3	4
Participation by members	1	2	3	4
Cohesion/friendship	1	2	3	4
Consensus	3	2	1	4
Flexibility	1	2	3	4
Individual productivity	2	1	3	4
Group productivity	3	2	1	4

(1 = effective 4 = least effective)

(Fleming, 2000)

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a team?

▪ *Commitment to a common purpose*

- the essence of a team;
- requires a purpose in which team members can believe (credible, meaningful, enthusiastic, a purpose that belongs to members both individually and collectively).

(Katzenbach & Smith, 1993, 2005)

If you want to build a ship, don't drum up people together to collect wood and don't assign them tasks and work, but rather teach them to long for the endless immensity of the sea.

Antoine de Saint-Exupery

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a team?

▪ *Specific performance goals*

- relate directly to the team's overall purpose;
- help define a set of work products that are different both from an organization-wide mission and from individual job objectives;
- facilitate clear communication and constructive conflict within the team;
- the attainability of specific goals helps teams maintain their focus on the results;
- have a levelling effect conducive to team behaviour;
- are compelling, they motivate and energize.

(Katzenbach & Smith, 1993, 2005)

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a team?

▪ *Complementary skills*

- *Technical skills* - are needed to meet the team's functional requirements
- *Problem-solving and decision-making skills* – are needed to identify problems and opportunities, evaluate options, make necessary trade-offs, and decide how to proceed
- *Interpersonal skills* – openness, active listening, feedback, support, trust, mutual influence, constructive confrontation

(Katzenbach & Smith, 1993, 2005)

What do you think of a team whose members were chosen primarily based on personal compatibility or formal position in the organization, and in which the skill mix of its members wasn't given much thought?

Co-funded by
the European Union

What is a team?

▪ *Mutual accountability*

- is based on **commitment** and **trust**;
- is about “putting our fates in the hands of others and accepting responsibility for others”;
- grows naturally when the team shares a common purpose, goals and approach.

(Katzenbach & Smith, 1993, 2005)

What is the difference between “the boss holds me accountable” and “we hold ourselves accountable in a team”?

Co-funded by
the European Union

2. The difference between a team and a working group

Working groups

- **Strong**, clearly focused leader
- **Individual** accountability
- The group’s purpose is **the same** as the broader organizational **mission**
- **Individual** work products
- Runs **efficient** meetings
- Measures its effectiveness indirectly by its **influence on others** (such as financial performance of the business)
- Discusses, decides and **delegates**

Teams

- **Shared** leadership roles
- **Individual and mutual** accountability
- **Specific** team purpose that the team itself delivers
- **Collective** work products
- Encourages **open-ended discussion** and **active problem-solving meetings**
- Measures its performance directly by assessing **collective work products**
- Discusses, decides, and does real work **together**

(Katzenbach & Smith, 2005)

Co-funded by
the European Union

3. When do we need a team?

YES

- when we are dealing with unusual problems, for which no one knows the answer and/ or there is no simple, standard answer;
- when there is a high degree of uncertainty (there is a strong need to share doubts with others);
- when there are tasks that require creativity;
- when the task is extremely complex and requires various skills and expertise;

NO

- when the task is simple and there is reduced uncertainty;
- when we deal with repetitive tasks, for which there are clear procedures;
- when the team has a very good reputation and „sits back on its laurels“;
- when the task must be solved very quickly (very short time);

(Necşoi, 2015; Fleming, 2000)

Co-funded by
the European Union

3. Why do we need a team?

YES

- achieves better results than the individuals;
- it is more flexible than a large group;
- takes more risks and explore areas that single individuals would avoid;
- generates a greater variety of ideas than individuals alone;
- members help each other, support each other in developing skills and increasing self-confidence;
- members demonstrate commitment / not only to the task, but also to each other;
- members motivate each other

NO

- there are social phenomena that disrupt the activity: "groupthink", "social laziness", the status effect, social compromise, social conformity;
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LqALdEvtTY4>
- concern for team cohesion overshadows the effectiveness of the task;
- requires time to form and strengthen relationships;
- it requires the transformation of people, and some are not willing to give up some beliefs and habits (negative and extremely critical attitude, manipulation, dominant behaviour, attacking the other person).

(Necşoi, 2015; Fleming, 2000)

Co-funded by
the European Union

4. Types of teams

- *permanent teams* vs. *temporary teams* (team members may come from the same department or different ones) =
- *natural work teams* vs. *problem solving teams*
- *Common types:*
 - *Project teams* are created for a specific period to achieve a specific goal. Often, members of a project team come from different functional groups and are chosen to participate in the project team based on their specific skills (e.g. software development).
 - *Virtual teams* combine people located in different places, often geographically dispersed; members come together to achieve a specific purpose (e.g. academic researchers).
 - *Cross-functional teams* have members from different domains, such as education and engineering, to solve a problem or achieve a goal (e.g. developing educational software or learning platforms).

Co-funded by
the European Union

Reflection:

- Give at least one example of a team you are currently working in.
- Characterize your team using the questions below:
 - ✓ What is the size of the team? Is it appropriate? Why?/ Why not?
 - ✓ What is the purpose of the team? Is it truly meaningful and understood?
 - ✓ Do members have sufficient complementary skills?
 - ✓ Are there team-oriented goals – are they clear, realistic, and measurable?
 - ✓ Does the team have a well thought-out, articulated working approach? What are the shared values of the team?
 - ✓ Is there a sense of mutual accountability? How do you achieve it?
- Explain why you think you and your colleagues belong to a team and not to a working group.

Katzenbach and Smith (1993)

Co-funded by
the European Union

5. The stages of team development

B. W. Tuckman model of group/ team development (1965)

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.workstyle.io/stages-of-team-development>

B. W. Tuckman model of group/ team development (1965)

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.workstyle.io/stages-of-team-development> (images without the description)

5. The stages of team development

▪ FORMING STAGE

Observable Behaviors

- Politeness
- Tentative joining
- Orienting with others personally
- Avoids controversy
- Cliques may form
- Need for safety and approval
- Attempts to define tasks, processes, and how it will be decided here
- Discussion of problems not relevant to the task

Feelings and Thoughts

- Many feel excited, optimistic, and full of anticipation
- Others may feel suspicious, fearful, and anxious working with others
- What is expected of me
- Why are they here
- Uncertainty and Apprehension

Team Needs

- Team mission and vision
- Establish specific objectives and tasks
- Identify roles and responsibilities of team members
- Establish team ground rules
- Team member expectations
- Operational guidelines for team
- Effective in class meetings
- Effective Chat meetings
- 1st set of feedback from project guides

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

5. The stages of team development

▪ STORMING STAGE

Observable Behaviors

- Arguing among members
- Vying for leadership
- Differences in points of view and personal style are evident
- Lack of role clarity
- Team organizing itself
- Power struggles and clashes
- Lack of consensus-seeking behaviors
- Lack of progress
- Establishes unrealistic goals
- Concern over excessive work

Feelings & Thoughts

- Feel Defensive
- Confusion, loss of interest can result
- Resistance to tasks
- Fluctuations in attitude about the team
- Unsure if I agree with teams mission and purpose
- Question the wisdom of team members
- Increase in tension and jealousy
- Unsure about my personal influence and freedom in the team
- We're not getting anywhere

Team Needs

- Inter & intra personal relationships
- Identify stylistic and personal differences
- Effective listening
- Giving and receiving feedback
- Conflict resolution
- Clarify and understand the team's purpose
- Reestablish roles and ground rules
- How to deal with 'some' team members violating team codes of conduct
- Receiving Feedback from project guide

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

5. The stages of team development

▪ NORMING STAGE

Observable Behaviors

- Processes and procedures are agreed upon
- Comfortable with relationships
- Focus and energy on tasks
- Effective conflict resolution skills
- Sincere attempt to make consensual decisions
- Balanced influence, shared problem solving
- Develop team routines
- Sets and achieves task milestones

Feelings & Thoughts

- Sense of belonging to a team
- Confidence is high
- Team members feel a new ability to express criticism constructively
- Acceptance of all members in the team
- General sense of trust
- Assured that everything is going to work out okay
- Freedom to express and contribute

Team Needs

- Develop a decision making process
- Be prepared to offer ideas and suggestions
- Problem solving is shared
- Utilizing all resources to support the team effort
- Team members take responsibility in shared leadership skills
- Receiving Feedback from project guides

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

5. The stages of team development

▪ PERFORMING STAGE

Observable Behaviors

- Fully functional teams
- Roles are clearer
- Team develops independence
- Team able to organize itself
- Flexible members function well individually, in subgroups or as a team
- Better understand each other's strengths and weaknesses and insights into group processes

Feelings & Thoughts

- Empathy for one another
- High commitment
- Begin understanding collaborative work ethic
- Tight bonds emerge
- Fun and excitement
- Lots of personal development and creativity
- General sense of satisfaction
- Continual discovery of how to sustain feelings of momentum and enthusiasm

Team Needs

- Project guides assure team is moving in collaborative direction
- Maintain team flexibility
- Measure knowledge performance – post test
- Provide information
- Giving and Receiving
- Feedback and Dialogue with project guides

Co-funded by the European Union

<https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

5. The stages of team development

Adjourning

▪ ADJOURNING STAGE

Observable Behaviors

- Visible signs of grief
- Momentum slows down
- Restless Behavior
- Bursts of extreme energy usually followed by lack of energy

Feelings & Thoughts

- Sadness
- Humor (that to outsiders could appear cruel)
- Glad it is over – relief

Team Needs

- Evaluate the efforts of the team
- Tie up loose ends and tasks
- Recognize and reward team efforts

Co-funded by
the European Union

<https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

Activity:

Team developmental stages

- Read carefully the statements in each quadrant and decide which ones do not correspond to that stage.
- (Hint: In each quadrant there are two statements that do not match.)
- Place them in the appropriate quadrant. Justify your option.

Co-funded by
the European Union

<p style="text-align: center;">Forming</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jane has doubts about the team, but she thinks it's worth a try. 2. Brian would have liked to know what role he plays in the team. 3. Fred wants to be part of a cohesive group. 4. Many of the team members complain that they fail to get together. 5. The team covers Carol's very poor work performance. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Storming</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As people get to know each other better, Jane notices a pattern of relationships within the team. 2. Jim makes secret comments about Fred's parental attitude. 3. Barbara is constantly trying to outdo the other members of the team. 4. Barbara feels good about sharing her ideas with the team. 5. John worries because he doesn't know for sure what things he is responsible for and what are the things that require teamwork.
<p style="text-align: center;">Norming</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The team members consider Jane, as a leader, responsible for coming up with solutions to all the problems that arise. 2. Brian is amazed at how well Tom and Jim get along. 3. John believes that mutual respect is responsible for the harmony of the team. 4. Barbara closely monitors the actions of Brian and Carol. 5. Team members support Jane in a dispute with the head of department. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Performing</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jane provides all the information necessary for the team to complete its task. 2. Fred feels more confident in his work when working in team. 3. John fears that teamwork will inhibit his creative genius. 4. The team strives to perform better than other teams in the department. 5. John is impressed with how innovative his team is.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity:

Teamwork Survey

- The participants will fill in a questionnaire based on the Tuckman Model, to identify the present stage of the teamwork model that their current team is operating in.
- The questionnaire is available at:

<http://www.nwlink.com/~donclark/leader/teamsuv.html>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity:

Team developmental stages

- Analyse the needs of the team at each of the five stages of its development.
- Identify leader behaviours needed to help the team through each stage, needed to help the team to resolve issues that arise and move toward performance.

Co-funded by
the European Union

5. The stages of team development –Tools for leaders

Forming:

- select the members according to the task;
- provide structure and task direction;
- clarify members' expectations;
- clarify the roles of members;
- create frequent contexts for members to get-acquainted;
- hold the first meeting of the team outside the official, formal context;
- give members the opportunity to choose their team;
- anticipate potential concerns and answer to possible questions of team members;
- create an atmosphere of confidence and optimism.

Co-funded by
the European Union

5. The stages of team development –Tools for leaders

Storming:

- look for signs/symptoms of conflict;
- be attentive to the people who are more often involved in conflicts (nonverbal language, reactions);
- resolve conflict situations as soon as they arise;
- teach conflict resolution methods;
- offer support and praise;
- give effective feedback;
- be attentive to the rumours about things that people are not satisfied with;
- encourage the team members to openly discuss any issue related to the team's activity.

Co-funded by
the European Union

29

5. The stages of team development –Tools for leaders

Storming:

- Watch out for people:
 - *expressing opinions about personalities and work methods;*
 - *testing the boundaries of roles;*
 - *challenging and jockeying for position;*
 - *revealing personal agendas;*
 - *opting out or feeling trapped;*
 - *showing signs of demotivation (Fleming, 2000).*

Co-funded by
the European Union

30

5. The stages of team development –Tools for leaders

Norming:

- clarify the rules the team operates by (limits of competence, limits of authority, allowed language and behaviours, etc.);
- allow the team to organize itself to practice its roles and responsibilities;
- encourage members to pay attention to the team functioning (encourage team reflexivity);
- create opportunities for members to recall the team's common values and goals;
- continue to build strong relationships.

Co-funded by
the European Union

31

5. The stages of team development –Tools for leaders

Performing:

- provide creative and enthusiastic tasks to the team;
- encourage humour, good mood, mutual support;
- encourage competition with other teams;
- encourage the team to practice shared leadership
- celebrate the success

Co-funded by
the European Union

32

Activity:

Labels

- The participants will be involved in a fun activity which demonstrates the impact labelling and dysfunctional team member behaviour have on both people and the work performance.

(Thorman and Mendonca, <https://hr.berkeley.edu>)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity:

Labels

- The group is divided into teams of six. Each team receives a set of six labels faced down. Labels should be large enough that participants can read them from several feet away, but small enough to fit on a person's forehead. Each participant sticks a label on the forehead of the person next to him/her. All participants can read what is on others' labels but not what is on their own. They shouldn't tell anyone what is on his/her own label.
- The teams receive a task to plan (plan a departmental picnic/ party). They will have 7 minutes to do this. As they discuss, they must engage with and react to each person on their team according to the label the person is wearing.
- After 7 minutes, even if the task is not complete, the teams are stopped.

(Thorman and Mendonca, <https://hr.berkeley.edu>)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity:

Labels. Debriefing

- What happened? Did you accomplish your task? Why or why not?
- How satisfied are you with the outcome? Why?
- How did you feel about treating people according to their assigned label? Did it get easier over time? If yes, why do you think that was?
- How did you feel about the way you were being treated? What was your reaction?
- What implications does this have for teams?

(Thorman and Mendonca, <https://hr.berkeley.edu>)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Activity:

Giving and receiving effective feedback

- The participants will be involved in an activity which offers the opportunity to build constructive strategies for overcoming the challenges of the storming stage. The participants will learn how to give and receive effective feedback as a member of a team.
- Feedback is a two-way communication: **giving** and **receiving**
- **Effective feedback** represents **objective information** about **behaviour** or **performance** of individuals and teams delivered in a **direct and respectful manner**, with **good intentions**, to improve performance and build success.
- **Specific, Immediate, Personal and Sincere**

Co-funded by
the European Union

36

Activity:

Giving and receiving effective feedback

▪ Feedback technique (1-2-3-4):

1. Say what the **problem** is – focus on **facts** and **examples**, focus on specific **behaviour** or **event** (*When you did...*)
2. Say how that made you **feel** or what it **affected**; name the emotion you feel, don't add *that* or *like* (*...it made me feel...*)
3. Describe the **effect** the behavior or event has on you and/or the team (*...because...*)
4. Suggest what could be **changed** – describe the **desired behaviour**, solutions or guidelines, clear expectations for improvement (*...and I'd rather you did... instead*)

Co-funded by
the European Union

37

Activity:

▪ Feedback technique (1-2-3-4) – Example 1:

1. *Emma, I notice that you interrupt me with questions when I'm presenting my work report in the team meeting each week. (the problem)*
2. *I feel frustrated when you do that (the emotion I feel)*
3. *... because it interrupts my train of thought and takes more time. (the effect on me)*
4. *I'd like you to hold your questions until I'm finished. I think you'll find that most of your questions will be answered in my report if you let me complete it before you ask questions. And, in this way, we'll be more effective! (the desired behaviour)*

Co-funded by
the European Union

38

Activity:

- Feedback technique (1-2-3-4) – Example 2:

1. *Yesterday, when you shouted at me in front of the team, (the problem)*
2. *I felt very awkward and disappointed, (the emotion I feel)*
3. *... because I invested a lot of efforts in this project which I feel are disregarded. (the effect on me)*
4. *Next time, I'd like you to tell me in private and on an appropriate tone what's bothering you. (the desired behaviour)*

Co-funded by
the European Union

39

Activity:

- Feedback technique (1-2-3-4) – Example 3 (positive feedback):

1. *Brian, thank you for getting your part of our team article to me early. (the event)*
2. *I was really relieved (the emotion I feel)*
3. *... to be able to get everyone's section combined and handed in before the final due date. Our coordinator was very impressed with our whole team's efficiency. (the effect)*
4. -

Co-funded by
the European Union

40

Activity:

Giving and receiving effective feedback

Read the following scenarios and use the 1-2-3-4 technique to give feedback to the persons in each situation.

1. Luke always pushes his team, and he often brings unnecessary stress. The team has planned to spend 5 days working on a project. But he wants them to be ready in just 3 days.
2. Maria is always available to help and explain things to her teammates. She expresses herself with great clarity. She can communicate effectively, and she is an active listener.
3. Grace is always trying to solve a problem with her current knowledge. Even if she knows that using another technology would be better, she will not read to get acquainted.
4. Charlie is a senior QA, who often expresses his discontent in front of the team when he must complete someone else's work. This distracts the team and brings tension.
5. Mia proactively informs people of decisions made when they were absent from a particular meeting. This is expected from everyone, but very often is missed.

<https://softskillspills.com/giving-feedback/#page>

41

Co-funded by
the European Union

Reflection:

Which of the statements below are true?

1. Since teamwork is a group experience, individuals can't be responsible for the quality of their team efforts.
2. Getting in a good team is mostly a matter of luck.
3. If you are in a poorly functioning team, and you are not in charge, there is little you can do but grin and bear it.
4. A team is only as strong as its strongest member.

Co-funded by
the European Union

42

Conclusions

- Teams and teamwork are increasingly relevant for organizations of all types, as globalization and technology expand organizational missions and strategies.
- Team performance and effectiveness are based on a clear understanding of the shared goals, strategies, and work plans, along with the individual roles and responsibilities of team members.
- Team's ability to achieve and sustain high performance is determined by a positive team dynamics characterized by trust, open communication, and mutual accountability.

Co-funded by
the European Union

43

• References (1):

- Bauer, T., Erdogan, E. (2012). *An introduction to organizational behaviour*. <http://2012books.lardbucket.org/>
- De Meuse, K. P. (2009). *Driving teams effectiveness. A comparative analysis of the Korn/Ferry T7 Model with other popular team models*. The Korn/Ferry Institute
- Eisenhardt, K., M., Kahwajy, J., L., Bourgeois L., J. (2000). How Management Teams Can Have a Good Fight. *Harvard Business Review* OnPoint Edition.
- Fleming, I. (2000). *The team working pocketbook*. Hampshire, UK: Management Pocketbooks Limited.
- Gunnarsson, M. (2010). *Group decision making*. Frederick, MD: Verlag
- Katzenbach, J., R., Smith, D., K. (1993). The discipline of teams, *Harvard Business Review* 83(7-8):162.
- Kroenhert, G. (1992). *100 training games*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Hughes, M. (2020). *8 Signs Groupthink May be Crippling Your Team*. <http://info.melissahughes.rocks/neuronugget/groupthink-is-it-killing-your-team-0>
- Hughes, M. (2018). Groupthink: Smiling and Nodding your Way to Defeat <https://www.melissahughes.rocks/post/groupthink-smiling-and-nodding-your-team-to-defeat>

Co-funded by
the European Union

44

• References (2):

- Katzenbach, J., R., Smith, D., K. (2005). The discipline of teams, *Harvard Business Review* OnPoint Edition 4428, July-August. <https://hbr.org/1993/03/the-discipline-of-teams-2>
- Katzenbach, J. R., & Smith, D. K. (1993). *The wisdom of teams: Creating the high-performance organization*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Lencioni, P., M. (2007). *The Five Dysfunctions of a Team: A Leadership Fable*. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons Print.
- Necşoi, D.V. (2015). Team and team management in *Journal Plus Education*, Vol. XII, no.1 (2015), (ISSN 1842 – 077X, E-ISSN (online) 317 – 328).
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (2011). *How we think: A theory of goal-oriented decision making and its educational applications*. New York, NY: Routledge
- Tuckman, B., W. (1965). Developmental sequence in small groups. *Psychological Bulletin*, 63(6), 384–399.
- Thorman, S., Mendonca, K. *Team Building Toolkit KEYS - Keys to Enhance Your Supervisory Success* University of California, Berkeley. <https://hr.berkeley.edu>
- West Chester University (n.d). *Tuckman's stages of group development*. <https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>

Co-funded by
the European Union

45

Thank
you

Co-funded by
the European Union

46